

DACEM

Digitized Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility

WP 2. Course Catalogues mapping and technical state of the art at
European HEIs

Activity 2.1 Course Catalogue mapping

Elaborated by:
Thessally University, Greece

21/05/2024

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

You are free to:

1. **Share** — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format for any purpose, even commercially.
2. **Adapt** — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.
3. The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give [appropriate credit](#), provide a link to the license, and [indicate if changes were made](#). You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or [technological measures](#) that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Please credit this report to:

“Heidmann, O. et al. (2024). Course Catalogue Mapping. DACEM Consortium.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14870536>”

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Title	Course Catalogue Mapping
Elaborated by	Thessally University, Greece
Contributors	Olivier Heidmann, Thessally University Dimitris Ziogas, Thessally University Adrian Lugilde López, University of Vigo Alenka Marušič, University of Maribor Anne Delouis, University of Orleans Bruna Gomes, Virtual Campus Carlos Vaz de Carvalho, Virtual Campus Elizaveta Getta, Charles University Fernando Ariel Mikic Fonte, University of Vigo Gabor Grosz, EUF Ioan Todinca, University of Orleans Jennifer Kroubo Dagnini, University of Orleans Manuel Caeiro Rodríguez, University of Vigo María Saar, Tallinn University Tiago Simões, EUF Uroš Kline, University of Maribor Vratislav Kozák, Charles University
Dates	21.05.2024
Status	Final Report
Activity related	Activity 2.1: Mapping current situation and requirements for online CC at European HEIs
Result N°	R2.1
Description	This report includes the identification and description of stakeholders and end-users of CC, and the description of main processes, use cases and requirements that are involved in the operation of existing CC. It also reviews current good practices and main problems in CCs.

Table of contents

1	INTRODUCTION	6
2	STAKEHOLDERS AND END-USERS	7
2.1	MANAGEMENT STAFF:	7
2.2	MOBILITY PURPOSES:	7
3	PROCESS OF OPERATING CCS	9
3.1	REQUIREMENTS	9
3.1.1	France	9
3.1.2	Greece	9
3.1.3	Spain	9
3.1.4	Portugal	10
3.1.5	Slovenia	10
3.1.6	Hungary	10
3.1.7	Estonia	10
3.1.8	Czechia	10
3.2	USE CASES	10
3.2.1	France	10
3.2.2	Greece	10
3.2.3	Spain	11
3.2.4	Portugal	11
3.2.5	Slovenia	11
3.2.6	Hungary	11
3.2.7	Estonia	11
3.2.8	Czechia	12
3.3	CONCLUSION	12
4	EXISTING CC SOLUTIONS	13
4.1	FRANCE	13
4.1.1	A generic example	14
4.1.2	Best CC examples	19
4.1.3	Other example	31
4.2	GREECE	34
4.2.1	Generic examples	35
4.2.2	Best CC examples	38
4.2.3	Other examples	41
4.3	HUNGARY	43
4.3.1	Generic examples	43
4.3.2	Best CC example	47
4.3.3	A wider picture	53
4.4	PORTUGAL	56
4.4.1	Generic examples	58
4.4.2	Best CC examples	66
4.5	SLOVENIA	66
4.5.1	Generic examples	78

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

4.5.2	<i>Best CC example</i>	82
4.6	SPAIN.....	84
4.6.1	<i>Generic examples</i>	85
4.6.2	<i>Best CC examples</i>	92
4.6.3	<i>Other examples</i>	103
4.7	ESTONIA.....	105
4.7.1	<i>Generic examples</i>	111
4.7.2	<i>Best CC examples</i>	111
4.8	CZECHIA.....	113
4.8.1	<i>Best CC examples</i>	113
4.9	SUMMARY.....	119
4.9.1	<i>Generic examples in every country</i>	119
4.9.2	<i>Best CC examples in every country</i>	121
4.9.3	<i>Other examples</i>	123
5	CONCLUSION	125
6	BIBLIOGRAPHY	127

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Introduction

The higher education systems in various countries have diverse structures, policies, and priorities, reflecting unique national contexts and aspirations. The DACEM consortium partners, from Hungary to Spain, Portugal to Greece, Estonia to Slovenia and Czechia illustrate that each nation's higher education system has distinct characteristics and challenges.

While each country faces its own unique set of challenges, such as accessibility and quality assurance, internationalization is a common theme across these diverse higher education landscapes. Initiatives like Erasmus+ and other mobility programs aim to promote collaboration, exchange, and mutual learning among nations, enriching their higher education sectors and preparing students for an increasingly interconnected world.

This report aims to explore and analyze the current state of course catalogues within these diverse higher education systems, shedding light on key trends, challenges, and opportunities in course information dissemination and student support. Through a comparative lens, the report seeks to gain insights that can enhance course catalogue practices, ultimately contributing to the broader goals of educational equity, excellence, and internationalization across these dynamic higher education landscapes.

The report is based on data collected from the higher education systems of the DACEM consortium countries, namely Hungary, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Estonia, Czechia and Slovenia. By leveraging the unique insights and experiences from these diverse nations, the report aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the current state of course catalogues, shedding light on key trends, challenges, and opportunities in course information dissemination and student support within the consortium.

The acronym "CC" will be commonly used instead of "Course Catalog" throughout this report.

Stakeholders and end-users

2.1 Management Staff:

University Administrators: Oversee the creation, updating, and distribution of CCs. They ensure that the information is accurate, up-to-date, and complies with institutional and national standards.

Academic Staff: Including professors and lecturers, use CCs to plan their courses and align them with the university's academic goals. They may also contribute to the content of the CCs.

Admissions Officers: Use CCs to provide prospective students with information about the courses available at the institution.

Quality Assurance Teams: Use CCs to assess the quality of the institution's academic offerings and ensure compliance with quality standards.

Curriculum Committees: Review and approve the courses listed in CCs, ensuring they meet educational objectives and institutional standards.

IT and Technical Support Staff: Maintain the online platforms and databases where CCs are published, ensuring accessibility and functionality.

2.2 Mobility Purposes:

Current Students: Use CCs to plan their academic path, choose their courses, and understand the requirements for their chosen degree.

Prospective Students: Use CCs to explore the courses offered by the institution and make informed decisions about their study choices.

Exchange Students: Rely on CCs to understand the courses they can take during their exchange period and how these courses can be credited back to their home institution.

Career Advisors: Use CCs to understand the skills and knowledge students gain from specific courses, helping them guide students toward suitable career paths.

Alumni: Refer to CCs for information on courses they have completed, which can be useful for further education or career advancement.

Employers and Industry Partners: Consult CCs to understand the competencies and qualifications of graduates, facilitating better recruitment and collaboration with the institution.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Government and Accreditation Bodies: Review CCs as part of the accreditation process to ensure that educational programs meet required standards and regulations.

International Offices: Use CCs to manage and coordinate international partnerships and student exchanges, ensuring academic compatibility and credit transfer.

Researchers: Access CCs to find relevant courses for collaboration and professional development or to identify gaps in the academic offerings that could be addressed through research initiatives.

By encompassing these additional roles, we acknowledge the broader spectrum of stakeholders who interact with course catalogues, highlighting the multifaceted importance of accurate and comprehensive course information in higher education.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Process of operating CCs

This chapter provides an overview of the process of operating course catalogues (CCs) in higher education institutions across France, Greece, Hungary, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Czechia and Estonia. It details the main processes involved, the requirements for operating CCs, and offers practical examples (use cases).

Requirements

The operation of course catalogues in higher education institutions (HEIs) involves several common requirements across the studied countries:

Autonomy in Management: HEIs generally have significant autonomy in scientific and pedagogical domains, allowing them to create, update, and distribute CCs. This autonomy includes developing curricula, defining course content, and determining teaching methodologies.

Regulatory Compliance: Institutions must comply with national and international regulations, which often require regular updates to CCs to reflect changes in course offerings, schedules, and academic policies. This ensures consistency, accessibility, and completeness of information.

Quality Assurance: Quality assurance agencies in each country, such as the Hellenic Authority for Higher Education (HAHE) in Greece and the Agency for Assessment and Accreditation of Higher Education (A3ES) in Portugal, oversee the quality and accreditation of educational programs, which impacts the content and structure of CCs.

Technological Infrastructure: The deployment of online platforms for managing CCs is crucial. These platforms must be user-friendly and accessible to all stakeholders, including students, academic staff, and administrative personnel.

France

The framework provided by the Ministry for Higher Education and Research (MESR), allows for universities a certain freedom to develop their own individual solutions concerning CC.

Greece

Collaboration within departments to compile comprehensive catalogues tailored to Erasmus students. Compliance with the Hellenic Authority for Higher Education (HAHE) ensures that catalogues meet national and international quality standards. Regular coordination among faculty members and feedback mechanisms from Erasmus participants help keep the catalogues up-to-date and relevant.

Spain

Compliance with standards set by bodies like ANECA (National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation). Universities must regularly update their CCs to reflect changes in course offerings, schedules, and academic policies, providing students with accurate and current information.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Portugal

Use of a centralized course assistant tool provided by the Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES) to help students navigate course options. This tool ensures that CCs are comprehensive, detailed, and accessible, including information on ECTS points, prerequisites, and program details, facilitating better academic planning and decision-making for students.

Slovenia

Ensuring that the CC is up-to-date, complete, and published on time as per ECHE requirements. Publishing the official CC by the end of March or early April, with updates only in exceptional cases.

Hungary

Creating and maintaining process workflows, timelines, and enforcing deadlines.

-Standardizing and validating course data, integrating it into a central repository, updating data, and maintaining the software and infrastructure for the CC IT system.

Estonia

According to the Higher Education Act, the workload for one academic year is 60 credits, equating to 26 hours of student work per credit. The academic year consists of ten study months divided into two semesters. In Tallinn University, the course schedules for the Autumn semester are published by the beginning of August, and for the Spring semester by the beginning of January. The TLU Academic Affairs Office is responsible for administering the Study Information System ÖIS2 and collecting and uploading the lists of Exchange Courses.

Czechia

In Czechia, higher education institutions ensure that their CCs are comprehensive, regularly updated, and compliant with national and international regulations.

Use Cases

France

In France, the Université d'Orléans updates its CCs regularly and ensures they are accessible to Erasmus students via online platforms. This includes detailed course descriptions and prerequisites to help students select appropriate courses.

Greece

Greek universities operate their CCs by collaborating within departments to compile comprehensive catalogues tailored to Erasmus students. These catalogues are regularly updated and uploaded to online platforms accessible to Erasmus coordinators and students. This process is

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

supported by academic advisors who assist students in aligning their course selections with their home universities' requirements.

Spain

In Spain, universities such as the University of Vigo (UVigo) and the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) use advanced online systems to manage their CCs. These systems include detailed information about course types, credit distribution, teaching methods, and languages of instruction. Quality assurance is maintained through regular updates and compliance with standards set by bodies like ANECA.

Portugal

Portugal's HEIs, such as the Polytechnic Institute of Porto and the University of Lisbon, ensure that their CCs are comprehensive and regularly updated. The Portuguese Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES) provides a centralized course assistant tool to help students navigate course options across different institutions.

Slovenia

Delivering Courses in English: All courses are taught in English. Course Selection in AIPS: The CC is published by faculty and study level, allowing students to select courses from multiple faculties. Detailed Course Information: Important course details are available in the application system. Publication on Website: CCs are published in PDF and Excel formats on the website for easy access and sorting.

Hungary

The provided information outlines essential responsibilities for managing a CC IT system. The key responsibilities include designing and managing process workflows and timelines, enforcing deadlines, gathering course, program, and organizational unit information using predefined templates, ensuring timely updates, monitoring legal and organizational changes, standardizing and validating course data, integrating data into a central repository, updating data, tracking changes, and maintaining the software and infrastructure for the CC IT system.

Estonia

At Tallinn University in Estonia, the operation of CCs involves several key components:

Academic Schedule Management: The academic year is divided into two semesters, each with 60 credits (26 hours of work per credit). Autumn semester schedules are published by early August, and Spring semester schedules by early January.

System Administration: The TLU Academic Affairs Office manages the Study Information System (ÕIS2). Erasmus coordinators from six academic units compile exchange course lists, which are uploaded to the Incoming Exchange Studies web page.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Course Information Requirements: All courses must have information in Estonian and English, including the title, assessment form, aims, description, and learning outcomes. Exchange courses are fully in English and part of international or Estonian programs with foreign language modules.

Use Cases:

Course Collection Timeline: Autumn semester exchange courses are updated by the end of March for student selection starting April 1. Spring semester courses are updated by the end of September for selection starting October 1. Updates are communicated to students as needed.

System Integration: Courses are managed and updated in the ÖIS2 system, with changes reflected on the web page and in SoleMove, the student course selection platform.

Czechia

Czechia's quality assurance agencies oversee the accreditation of educational programs, emphasizing the importance of accurate and up-to-date course information. Institutions such as Charles University and Masaryk University utilize advanced online systems to manage their CCs, providing detailed information about course offerings, credit distribution, and academic policies. Regular updates and compliance with national and international standards ensure the quality and accessibility of course information for students and academic staff.

Conclusion

The operation of course catalogues in European HEIs involves a structured process that ensures autonomy, regulatory compliance, and quality assurance. The requirements and use cases from France, Greece, Spain, Portugal, Czechia and Slovenia highlight the importance of regular updates, stakeholder accessibility, and technological infrastructure in maintaining effective CCs. For Hungary and likely Estonia, detailed management and IT responsibilities ensure the efficient operation of CC systems. This unified approach across different countries facilitates academic mobility and ensures high-quality education standards.

Existing CC solutions

France

In a nutshell, French universities either use ad-hoc solutions or the AMETYS Campus software. [AMETYS Campus](#) is an open-source platform offered by the [AMETYS](#) company, working mainly on data management for education and local authorities. Although the software is open-source and can be interfaced with APOGEE, its implementation requires considerable organisational and procedural work within universities.

According to our observations, French HEIs fall into two groups: some develop their own custom-made IT solutions for CCs. The others use AMETYS, among which (advertised on the AMETYS website):

- Université Savoie Mont-Blanc
- Université de Toulouse
- Université Paris Cité
- Université de Nîmes
- Université Paris Sud
- Institut national polytechnique de Toulouse
- Université de Poitiers

The Université d'Orléans is transitioning towards AMETYS as well.

[Campus France](#), the French Agency for the promotion of higher education, international student services, and international mobility, purports to present study programmes of French HEIs on its website, but the catalogue does not seem to work at the time of writing (technical errors).

<https://cataloguem.campusfrance.org/licence/#/catalog?lang=en>

Table 1: List of main CCs in France

Institution	CC Web address	Generic information	Resources and Services	Programmes	Individual Educational Components
Université de Reims Champagne Ardennes	https://www.univ-reims.fr/	Fully available	Information available on pages specifically dedicated to international students	Good availability - French	Not available
INSA Rouen Normandie	https://www.insa-rouen.fr/en	Fully available	Information available on pages specifically dedicated to	Good availability	Partially available

			international students		
Université de Montpellier	https://www.univ-montpellier.fr/en/	Fully available	Information available on pages specifically dedicated to international students	Good availability	Available to fully available
Université Savoie Mont Blanc	https://formati-ons.univ-smb.fr/fr/index.html	Fully available	Information available on pages specifically dedicated to international students	Average availability - French	Available - French
Université d'Orléans	https://www.univ-orleans.fr/fr	Fully available	Information available on pages specifically dedicated to international students	Average availability - French	Not available

A generic example

The University of Reims Champagne Ardennes [URCA CC](#) makes some efforts to tend towards required European standards and provides a relatively satisfying level of information on its CC – translated in English.

On the English version of its internet website, you can proceed by the following research to find courses that you can have an interest for: **“Study at URCA > Courses > Research by degree”**.

Figure 1 . Screen shot of URCA CC research approach by degree courses

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Figure 2 . Screen shots of URCA CC list of the different fields of study by level

Users can move through the level intended and then find a list by field of studies. Clicking on a field of study, they find all the degree courses offered in the domain they are interested in.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Figure 3 Screen shots of URCA CC list of degree courses by field of study as well as level

Unfortunately, to find more details about the degree course chosen, the website switches back to the French version by itself, even for the degree courses involving foreign languages such as the bachelor for “applied foreign languages”.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The figure consists of two screenshots of the University of Reims Champagne Ardenne website. Both screenshots show a dark blue header with the university's logo and name, and a navigation menu with 'Université', 'Formation', 'Recherche, innovation et valorisation', and 'Orientation et Insertion'. A yellow sidebar on the left contains a '+' icon and the word 'Rubriques'. The main content area has a teal background.

Top Screenshot: Licence Langues étrangères appliquées
parcours Anglais-espagnol (Troyes)
CATALOGUE DE LA RENTREE 2024-2025

- Domaine : [Arts, lettres, langues](#)
- Type de formation : [Licence](#)
- Localisation : [Troyes](#)
- Faculté, Ecole, Institut... : [UFR Lettres et Sciences Humaines](#)
- Public concerné : [Formation Initiale](#), [Formation Continue](#)
- Modalités d'enseignement : [Présentiel](#)
- Niveau à l'entrée en formation : niveau IV (BP, BT, baccalauréat professionnel ou technologique)
- Niveau à la sortie de la formation : niveau II (licence ou maîtrise universitaire)

Bottom Screenshot: Master Lettres et humanités
parcours Littérature, culture, création
CATALOGUE DE LA RENTREE 2024-2025

- Domaine : [Arts, lettres, langues](#)
- Type de formation : [Master](#)
- Localisation : [Reims](#)
- Faculté, Ecole, Institut... : [UFR Lettres et Sciences Humaines](#)
- Public concerné : [Formation Initiale](#), [Formation Continue](#)
- Modalités d'enseignement : [Présentiel](#)
- Niveau à l'entrée en formation : niveau II (licence ou maîtrise universitaire)
- Niveau à la sortie de la formation : niveau I (supérieur à la maîtrise)

Figure 4 Screen shots of URCA CC degree courses detailed – in French

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Similar to our generic example, most French HEIs do not fully comply with the ECTS Users' Guide, although they are making some efforts to do so.

Best CC examples

Example 1. The National Institute for Applied Sciences [INSA Rouen Normandie](#)

It has developed a course catalogue with detailed information about each teaching unit. The descriptive categories include:

- Course title and code
- Degree programme
- Semester, study track
- Duration
- Teaching language
- Study outcomes
- Study prerequisites
- Course content ("programme")
- Course type (lecture, seminar or other)
- Evaluation
- Recommended reading
- Teaching staff (name, job position)

INSA INSA Rouen Normandie

ÉNERGÉTIQUE ET PROPULSION

ATOMISATION ET SPRAYS

Semestre 9 / Parcours Energies Durables / Systèmes Energétiques Utilisation de l'Energie

L1 L2 L3 M1 M2 | Référence : EP51-ATOM | Nombre d'heures : 12 h | ICF EN

* Etre capable d'appréhender un problème de production de gouttes liquides par un système d'injection.
 * Etre capable de caractériser les performances d'un injecteur (débit, coefficient de décharge, ζ).
 * Etre capable de représenter et d'analyser une distribution de taille de gouttes d'un spray.
 * Etre capable de choisir le diagnostic approprié pour mesurer une granulométrie de spray.
 To introduce the main physical concepts in atomization. Definition of the basic tools to treat a problem related to the atomization
 * Being able to study the droplet production from an injection system.
 * Being able to characterize the performances of a nozzle (flow rate, discharge coefficient, ζ)
 * Being able to represent and analyze a drop size distribution of a liquid spray.
 * Being able to choose the appropriate diagnostic to measure a spray granulometry.

Prérequis

- * Base de physique, mécanique des fluides
- Basics in physics, fluid mechanics
- * Basics in physics, fluid mechanics

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

<p>■ Programme</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Généralités sur les sprays * Domaines d'applications * Propriétés physiques des fluides affectant l'atomisation * Caractérisation des écoulements dans les injecteurs. * Application aux injecteurs à swirl (caractérisation, modélisation) * Fonctionnement des injecteurs automobiles * Eléments physiques utiles à l'étude de l'atomisation * Description des distributions de taille des gouttes d'un spray * Modélisation des distributions de taille des gouttes d'un spray * Eléments sur les techniques de mesure de distributions de taille et de vitesses <p>Generalities on sprays</p> <p>Applications</p> <p>Physical properties of fluids</p> <p>Characterisation of flows in nozzles</p> <p>Case of pressure swirl atomizers (characterization, modeling)</p> <p>Case of automotive injectors</p> <p>Physical aspects to study the atomization</p> <p>Introduction of the stability analysis (linear theory)</p> <p>Applications on flat liquid sheets and cylindrical jets</p> <p>Description of the spray drop size distribution</p> <p>Modelling of the spray drop size distribution</p> <p>Notions in measurement techniques to retrieve the joint drop size-velocity distributions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Generalities on sprays * Applications * Physical properties of fluids * Characterization of flows in nozzles * Case of pressure swirl atomizers (characterization, modeling) * Case of automotive injectors * Physical aspects to study the atomization * Description of the spray drop size distribution * Modelling of the spray drop size distribution * Notions in measurement techniques to retrieve the joint drop size-velocity distributions
<p>↳ Évaluation</p>	<p>ECRIT E2 ECRIT : Examen écrit E2 : ECRIT SESSION 2</p>
<p>Types d'enseignement</p>	<p>CM CM : Atomisation et sprays</p>
<p>Calcul de la note finale</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Un examen écrit 1 written exam
<p>📖 Lectures conseillées</p>	<p>Atomization and Sprays, A. Lefebvre, Hemisphere Publishing Corporation, 1989</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Atomization and Sprays, A. Lefebvre, Hemisphere Publishing Corporation, 1989

Liste des intervenants

Responsable JEAN COUSIN - *Directeur département EP / Enseignant en Mécanique des Fluides*
YVES D ANGELO - *Enseignant EP5 Combustion dans les MCI*

Figure 5 Screen shots of INSA Rouen Normandie (school of Engineering) CC

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

At the moment, some course descriptions are incomplete (for example, no recommended reading or no prerequisites), and not all have been translated into English. However, the template is excellent.

Example 2: The University of Montpellier <https://www.umontpellier.fr/en/>

A good example of what French universities are able to tend towards in terms of good practices to communicate about their educational offer, especially with international students as end-users in mind.

8 faculties, 7 institutes, 2 schools

Figure 6 Screen shots of the University of Montpellier CC 1st pages

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The user can browse through the whole catalogue by either keyword, degree, faculty (composante), field of study, language of instruction and even campus location.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Figure 7 Screen shot of the University of Montpellier CC different ways to search for a degree course

Filters (here, faculty of pharmacy) lead to a handy, visually appealing interface. The menu gives access to full details per year and per semester, and the content of each course. Below is an example of a Master taught at the faculty of Science - [Master in computer science](#). Among other general information, the webpage contains a summary of the syllabus, the detailed syllabus, the number of ECTS per course and the targeted skills and competencies. It even addresses the career opportunities after obtaining the diploma.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Training courses ▾ Work-study programs (apprenticeship)

Presentation

Organization

Program

Admission

And then

Presentation

The **Master's in Computer Science** is structured into **five** clearly identified **courses** with undifferentiated research and professional goals. These five tracks aim to train computer science managers with skills in architecture, software and information systems design, data management and exploitation, modeling and combinatorial optimization, web and network technologies, image processing, especially 3D, and language and natural language processing. These five courses are : **Algo (Algorithmics)**, **GL (Software Engineering)**, **Imagine (Image and Video Games)**, **IASD (Artificial Intelligence and Data Science)**, **ICo (Competency Integration)**

For students who have validated a Bachelor's degree in Computer Science with the CMI label (Cursus Master Ingénierie) it is possible to follow the CMI curriculum in the Algorithmics (Algo), Software Engineering (GL), Imagine (Imagine) and Artificial Intelligence and Data Science (IASD) courses. As a reminder, the Master's Degree in Computer Science Engineering is a demanding and reinforced 5-year program that completes the Bachelor's - Master's Degree in Computer Science program by adding specific courses. The CMI has been developed as a complementary model for training in engineering professions through a five-year diploma course leading to a Master's degree in Engineering, corresponding to the international Master of Engineering model. This CMI label guarantees a coherent and demanding university training program for the profession of expert engineer. Upon completion of the CMI Informatique, graduates obtain a Master of Management from the Institut d'Administration des Entreprises (IAE), the Figure network label, as well as a university diploma (D.U.) for the Master of Engineering - Computer Science program. The CMI Computer Science is open to Master 2 students on a sandwich basis.

For students wishing to co-diploma IAE Master Management of Technology and Science: possibility offered (on file) to achieve in parallel with the initial training a management training giving the degree of Master in Management of Technology and Science. Over the two years of training, the curriculum alternates courses in computer science (taught by the FdS) and management (taught by the IAE) with a common internship validated by both components in the second year. This co-diplomation allows students to exit with the master **Computer Science** and the master **Management of Technologies and Sciences**.

Lire moins

Objectives

- Algo (Algorithmics)**
 This course provides students with a deep understanding of the discipline, combined with more specialized know-how in algorithms, operations research, or theoretical computer science.
- GL course (Software Engineering)**
 This course is located in the field of software engineering and proposes in particular a training which is interested in the automation of the stages of the software life cycle while ensuring the quality of the software product, from the design to the maintenance while passing by the compilation and the optimization of the code and the test.
- Imagine course (image and video games)**
 This course aims to train engineers and researchers specializing in image and vision industries and laboratories, computer graphics, virtual and augmented reality, video games and interactive simulation.
- IASD course (Artificial Intelligence and Data Science)**
 This Artificial Intelligence and Data Science course trains specialists with a high level of programming skills in the design and development of intelligent information systems and automatic data analysis.
- ICo course (Integration of Competences)**
 This course offers a generalist computer science training in 2 years to acquire a double competence in computer science and initial training and/or to start a reconversion in computer science. It differs from the other courses in the Master's program in computer science, in that it is aimed at students with initial training other than in computer science, in order to offer them the opportunity to acquire the concepts essential for mastering the current challenges of digital technology.

Lire moins

Summary of the training

Diploma	Master
Nature	Diploma
Discipline(s)	Computer Science
Input level	BAC +3
Mandatory entry level	No
RNCP level	Level 7
Study plan	Initial training Continuing education Work-linked training
Location(s)	Montpellier - Trinité

Teaching location

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Knowledge control

<https://mcc.umontpellier.fr/> groups all the teaching units (UE) and their knowledge control methods.

Open in alternation

Type of contract Apprenticeship contract, Professionalization contract

Alternation methods

The second year (M2) can be done on a sandwich basis, via **professionalization or apprenticeship contracts**. The **alternating** student becomes an employee for the duration of his or her M2 (under contract generally from September 1 to August 31). The academic year takes the following form: during the course/TD/TP period, the alternating student is at the faculty to follow the courses; during the university vacation and internship periods, the alternating student is in the company (1 week in November, 2 weeks in December, and from the last week of January to August 31; this makes a presence in the company of 8 months out of 12).

We remind you here that a professionalization or apprenticeship contract is a tripartite contract between student, company and university: the agreement of the head of the service is necessary. Its content is based on the academic results of the IUT and on the opinion of the course leader. This is available

[Read more](#) +

Internships, tutored projects

Internship	Mandatory
Duration of the course	5
Internship abroad	Possible
Duration of the internship abroad	5

The second semester of the M2 is dedicated to the end-of-study internship lasting 5 months in an industrial or academic environment (depending on its nature).

Select a program

Algorithms

The **Algo** course of the Master of Computer Science prepares students for the most demanding jobs in the world of computer science. It provides students with a deep understanding of the computer science discipline, combined with more specialized know-how in algorithms, operations research, or theoretical computer science. This program trains students to become major players in computer science, by insisting on a solid foundation of knowledge ranging from the most fundamental concepts to their practical application in specialized programs. Thus the student, once he or she has become a young computer scientist, will be able to evolve serenely throughout his or her career, by easily adapting to new concepts and to the evolution inherent to the discipline. The career opportunities of this program are mainly in research and development teams in the computer industry, as well as in specialized research in industry or in the academic world.

For students who have validated a Bachelor's degree in Computer Science with the CMI label (Cursus Master Ingénierie) It is possible to follow the CMI curriculum in the Algorithmics (Algo), Software Engineering (GL), Imagine (Imagine) and Artificial Intelligence and Data Science (IASD) courses. As a reminder, the Master's Degree in Computer Science Engineering is a demanding and reinforced 5-year program that completes the Bachelor's - Master's Degree in Computer Science program by adding specific courses. The CMI has been developed as a complementary model for training in engineering professions through a five-year diploma course leading to a Master's degree in Engineering, corresponding to the International Master of Engineering model. This CMI label guarantees a coherent and demanding university training program for the profession of expert engineer. Upon completion of the CMI Informatique, graduates obtain a Master of Management from the Institut d'Administration des Entreprises (IAE), the Figure network label, as well as a university diploma (D.U.) for the Master of Engineering - Computer Science program. The CMI Computer Science is open to Master 2 students on a sandwich basis.

For students wishing to co-diploma IAE Master Management of Technology and Science: possibility offered (on file) to achieve in parallel with the initial training a management training giving the degree of Master in Management of Technology and Science. Over the two years of training, the curriculum alternates courses in computer science (taught by the FdS) and management (taught by the IAE) with a common internship validated by both components in the second year. This co-diplomation allows students to exit with the master **Computer Science** and the master **Management of Technologies and Sciences**.

[See the complete page of this course](#) +

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

How to register

Applications are made via the platforms :

- Nationals and European Community: "My Master" from the website: <https://www.monmaster.gouv.fr/>
- Outside the EU: "Studies in France" since: <https://pastel.diplomatie.gouv.fr/etudesenfrance/dyn/public/authentication/login.html>

Capacity

150

And then

Further studies

Doctorate (competitive examination).

Professional integration

- In the private sector: Engineer (study, research and development), researcher, architect, administrator, project manager, consultant, developer, analyst, ... Its functions touch a very large number of fields: software development, information systems, multimedia, web, databases, artificial intelligence, embedded systems, video games, bioinformatics, geomatics, etc...
- In the public sector: University teacher-researcher, researcher or engineer (study, research) in public research organizations (CNRS, INRIA, ...).

Figure 8. Screen shots of the University of Montpellier detailed page of the Master in computer science degree course

The compliance with the ECTS user guide is rather good. In particular, the general information, the information on programmes and the individual educational components are well described. As it is often the case with French universities, the resources and services are described in separate sections of the website such as the international webpages (<https://www.umontpellier.fr/en/international/etudier-a-letranger>).

Example 3: the University of Savoie Mont Blanc uses AMETYS Campus.

Its course catalogue is mainly in French but it is rather well-organised and illustrates the potential of this platform.

As depicted below, the user can browse through the whole catalogue by either keyword, degree, faculty (composante) or campus. The last option is particularly relevant for universities with campuses in different cities. In this example, the Savoie Mont Blanc university has three main campuses in three different cities, Annecy, Chambéry and Bourget-du-Lac.

Figure 9 Screen shot of the University of Savoie Mont Blanc CC 1st page

A clickable graphic interface provides an overview by degree: bachelor, bachelor of technology, master, doctorate, engineering degree, etc.

Figure 10 Screen shot of the University of Savoie Mont Blanc motor research by degree level and field of study page

Filters (here, bachelor) lead to a handy, visually appealing interface.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

23 formations

Licence Droit
Droit, Économie, Gestion
Licence
La Licence Droit offre aux étudiants, au cours des deux premières années de licence, une formation généraliste leur permettant de se familiariser avec les matières juridiques fondamentales du droit...

L3 - Droit privé
L3 - Droit public

Ajouter à la sélection Télécharger

Licence Economie et gestion
Droit, Économie, Gestion
Licence
La Licence mention « Économie-Gestion », accessible dès la L1, est une formation pluridisciplinaire couvrant plusieurs domaines tels que le management, l'économie, les sciences informatiques...

Figure 11 Screen shot of the University of Savoie Mont Blanc degree list example

When zooming on a specific degree (here, the bachelor of informatics), the webpage presents a summary of the contents, the course duration, student testimonials, etc. The “Admission” menu indicates the prerequisites and provides the main administrative information for students (included high school ones).

DIPLOME NATIONAL DE LICENCE CONTRÔLÉ PAR L'ÉTAT

Niveau de diplôme: BAC +3
ECTS: 180 crédits
Durée: 3 années, 6 semestres
Langues d'enseignement: Français

Présentation Organisation Programme Admission Et après

Présentation

La licence Informatique permet d'acquérir les compétences scientifiques et techniques indispensables au développement d'applications numériques. Cette licence propose des enseignements pour les fondements de l'informatique (algorithmique, structures de données, systèmes d'exploitation) ainsi qu'en génie logiciel (programmation, bases de données, gestion de projets, etc.).

L'apprentissage par projets est favorisé. En effet, la réalisation d'un logiciel pour une société ou une association permet aux étudiants de saisir les différents aspects du cycle de vie du logiciel, depuis l'acquisition des besoins jusqu'à la livraison. A cette occasion, les méthodes agiles sont abordées, ainsi que la gestion humaine, la prise en compte du client, et les outils facilitant le développement collaboratif.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Figure 12 Screen shot of the University of Savoie Mont Blanc detailed page of the License degree in Computer Science

The “programme” menu gives access to full details per year and per semester, and the content of each course. Here is an example of an [Algorithms and programming course](#) - the webpage also contains the detailed syllabus, and the targeted skills and competencies.

Description

Algorithmique et programmation en Python

Objectifs

Donner à tout étudiant les bases de la programmation. Faire en sorte que tous arrivent à un niveau de maîtrise suffisant pour pouvoir démarrer, au semestre 2, un apprentissage de la résolution de problèmes (choix du modèle de données adapté, analyse du problème, décomposition en sous-problèmes, réalisation de la décomposition fonctionnelle).

Heures d'enseignement

🕒 Algorithmique - CM	Cours Magistral	6h
🕒 Algorithmique - TD	Travaux Dirigés	9h
🕒 Algorithmique - TP	Travaux Pratiques	12h

En bref

- 🌐 Langues d'enseignement Français
- ★ Méthodes d'enseignement En présenc
- 🌐 Ouvert aux étudiants en échange Oui

Lieux

Le Bourget-du-Lac (73)

Campus

Le Bourget-du-Lac / campus Savoie Technolac

Figure 13 Screen shot of the University of Savoie Mont Blanc detailed contents of the Algorithms & programming course taught in the License degree course in Computer Science

Although even Savoie Mont Blanc University still lacks descriptions of some courses, their website is a good illustration of the capabilities of AMETYS Campus. It appears that the structure of the website is extracted from APOGEE (see Section 3.1), and then the content is (more or less) completed with details. AMETYS Campus allows procedures and workflows to distribute the work, particularly among administration and teaching staff. In particular, the teaching staff can fill in the syllabus, learning outcomes, skills and prerequisites, when the rest is already present in the information system (e.g., APOGEE). It also handles multiple academic years, e.g., the catalogue of 2023-2024 and 2024-2025 may coexist. The course catalogue can be exported as a PDF file.

The compliance with the ECTS user guide is not perfect but fairly good. In particular, the general information, the information on programmes and the individual educational components are

well described. The resources and services are described in a separate [Information and guidance](#) section of the website.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Other example

Figures 1 & 2 show the main interface of the University of Orleans CC, with the browsing and search options available. The English version of the pages is published with a tree-like structure and includes translations, but when you examine the details, you encounter a list that lacks further links for additional information.

Figure 14 Screen shot of the University of Orleans CC

Portal > Courses by Degree

The screenshot shows a web interface for 'Courses by Degree'. On the left is a dark grey navigation menu with the following items: 'Courses Catalogue', 'Attractive Courses', 'Courses by Degree' (highlighted in blue), 'Courses by Place', 'Courses by Department', 'All Courses', 'Application and Registration', 'Registration Fees', 'Transfer Procedures', 'Studies Organisation', 'Collecting Your Diploma', and 'Lifelong Learning'. On the right, the main content area is titled 'Courses by Degree' and lists 'BUTs (University Bachelors of Technology)' under three categories: 'Law, Economics, Management' (with three courses: B.U.T. GEA Business and Administration Management, B.U.T. GLT Transportation and Logistics Management, and B.U.T. TC Marketing Techniques), 'Humanities and Social Sciences' (with one course: B.U.T. CS Careers in Social Services Option Urban Management), and 'Science, Technology and Health' (with two courses: B.U.T. Chemistry OPTION Analytical and Synthetic Chemistry and B.U.T. Industrial Engineering and Maintenance GIM).

Figure 15 Screen shot of the degree courses offered at the University of Orleans CC

Figure 3 shows the tool the University of Orleans has been using for a decade. It is missing some English contents.

If you try to search for a keyword in English, the few programmes entirely taught in English are the only ones that will be found.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Courses

- Courses Catalogue
- Attractive Courses**
- Courses by Degree
- Courses by Place
- Courses by Department
- All Courses
- Application and Registration
- Registration Fees
- Transfer Procedures
- Studies Organisation
- Collecting Your Diploma
- Lifelong Learning
- Observatory of Student Life
- Succeeding with Digital Technologies

All Courses

Search the course catalogue of the University of Orléans below.

RECHERCHER UNE FORMATION

Intitulé

Mots clés

Diplôme
- Tous (150) -

Composante
- Tous (150) -

Lieu(x)
- Tous (150) -

Rechercher

Figure 16 . Screen shot of the research tool (AMETYS) used at the University of Orleans CC

As mentioned before, the University of Orléans currently deploys a more advanced version of AMETYS and will soon be able to offer a better CC.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Greece

Greek universities generally provide information about their Course Catalogs (CCs) to some extent. Table 1 presents a list of Greek universities along with details regarding their CCs. This list is considered representative of the general situation in the country. Most universities have CC solutions similar to the first 2 universities listed (e.g., University of Thessaly and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki). The University of Crete (UoC) has the best CC solution found. Other universities may have CC information scattered across various sections of their institutional websites (University of Patras and National and Kapodistrian University of Athens). Consequently, accessing all the information outlined in the ECTS Users' Guide directly may not always be feasible.

Table 2: List of main CCs in Greece

Institution	CC Web address	Generic information	Resources and Services	Programmes	Individual Educational Components
University of Thessaly	https://erasmus.uh.gr/en/studies-en/courses-en	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	https://eurep.auth.gr/en/students/info/courses	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Crete	https://en.uoc.gr/studies-at-uni/course-catalog-2022-23.html	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Patras	Institutional website: https://www.upatras.gr/en/	Fully available	Fully available	Partially available	Partially available
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Institutional website: https://en.uoa.gr/	Fully available	Partly available	Fully available	Fully available

Generic examples

University of Thessaly (UTH)

The University of Thessaly has a streamlined and user-friendly CC for courses offered in English, consolidating most of the essential information onto a single web page. Each department is conveniently listed with direct links to PDF documents containing detailed course descriptions, semester schedules, and ECTS points. This efficient layout helps visiting students to find important information.

Erasmus+ Enriching lives, opening minds

Courses

1. COURSES IN ENGLISH

The University of Thessaly also offers courses in English. Since the academic year 2017-18, there is a list of all available courses per Department taught in English. The list is updated at the beginning of each academic year. Our priority is to multiply the courses taught in English in the University of Thessaly in the following years.

Academic Year 2023-2024

VOLOS

- [Department of Architecture](#)
- [Department of Culture, Creative Media and Industries](#)
- [Department of Economics](#)
- [Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering](#)
- [Department of History, Archaeology & Social Anthropology](#)
- [Department of Language and Intercultural Studies](#)
- [Department of Mechanical Engineering](#)
- [Department of Planning & Regional Development](#)
- [Department of Primary Education](#)
- [Department of Special Education \(only in Spring Semester\)](#)

LARISSA

Search...

- Announcements
- Documents
- Erasmus Student Network
- Photo Gallery
- Videos - Presentations
- Useful Links
- Contact

Figure 17 . Screen shot of programmes page in the UTh website

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

As shown in Figure 2 each catalog includes information about the semester, course code, title and ECTS. The instructor field is left blank. Although the given info is well organized, the CCs lack important information such as the scientific field of each course and the name of the instructor.

However, the full lists of the active courses (in Greek) are found in the institutional website of each department. More details can be found by searching for the specific course code which is rather inconvenient and time consuming. One positive thing is that for the majority of the departments there is an English version for each course's description.

UNIVERSITY OF
THESSALY

DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING
SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

SEMESTER	COURSE CODE	COURSE	ECTS	INSTRUCTOR
WS	ECE119	Digital Design (Core)	6	
WS	ECE317	Artificial Intelligence (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE319	Compilers (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE321	Concurrent Programming (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE325	Digital Signal Processing (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE327	Digital Systems VLSI (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE329	Education Technologies (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE331	Electrical Machines (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE333	Digital Systems Lab (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE337	Linear Programming (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE339	Applied Statistics (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE335	Electric Power Generation Systems (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE341	Advanced Electronics (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE411	Power Systems II (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE415	High Performance Computing Systems (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE419	Logical and Functional Programming (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE447	Neuro-Fuzzy Computing (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE449	Smart Grids (Elective)	6	
WS	ECE437	Electrical Installations (Elective)	6	

Figure 18 List of available courses for the department of Electrical Engineering

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

Similar to University of Thessaly the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki does not have a proper CC provided as a result by the Google search engine, but the CC information can be found at the institutional web site and at several faculties and schools web sites. As shown in Figure 3, there is a table with links for every department of the university.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

<https://eurep.auth.gr/en/coordinators/studies>

SCHOOLS	WEBLINK – COURSES AVAILABLE FOR ERASMUS+ STUDENTS	ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
SCHOOL OF THEOLOGY	Undergraduate Study Programme: https://qa.auth.gr/en/studyguide/60000024/current Postgraduate Study Programme: https://qa.auth.gr/en/studyguide/600000289/current	
SCHOOL OF SOCIAL THEOLOGY AND CHRISTIAN CULTURE	https://past.auth.gr/en/studies/international-exchange-programs-erasmus/... 2023-2024: https://past.auth.gr/en/studies/undergraduate-studies/available-courses/	
SCHOOL OF LAW	https://law.auth.gr/en/erasmus-courses/	
SCHOOL OF ECONOMIC SCIENCES	https://t.ly/dG2ub	
SCHOOL OF POLITICAL SCIENCES	Open Courses in English: Greece Today (Fall/Spring) Greek Politics (Fall) Educational Practices and Politics (partly in English) (Fall) Political Systems in the Balkans (Spring) Solidarity and Cohesion in the European Union (Fall) Politics and Government in Southern Europe. A Comparative Analysis (Spring) Religion and Politics (Spring) Constitutional law of the EU (Winter) History and institutions of the EU (Winter) Euroscepticism: parties, policies and people (Winter) EU Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (Spring) EU Governance and Policies (Spring) Fundamental rights in Europe (Spring) EU-Africa relations (Spring)	You can see all the courses in English at the page below: https://www.polsci.auth.gr/en/basic_page_polsci/courses-taught-in-english/ All other courses (see here: https://www.polsci.auth.gr/en/course-list/) are taught in the Modern Greek Language. However, examination/evaluation in foreign languages is available for the incoming students, upon compliance with the professors.
SCHOOL OF JOURNALISM AND MASS MEDIA COMMUNICATION	Fall Semester: https://www.jour.auth.gr/en/erasmus-plus-international/courses-in-englis... Spring Semester: https://www.jour.auth.gr/en/erasmus-plus-international/courses-in-englis...	All courses are taught in English both at the undergraduate and postgraduate programme.
SCHOOL OF PHILOLOGY	https://www.lit.auth.gr/en/node/1555	All the courses are taught in the Modern Greek Language. However, examination/evaluation in foreign languages is available for the incoming students, upon compliance with the professors.

Figure 19 Screen shot of programmes page in the AUTH web site

As shown in Figure 4, similar to UTh most catalogs include information about the semester, course code, title and ECTS. Although the given info is well organized, some CCs lack important information such as the scientific field of each course and the name of the instructor and description. One downside is that each department has a completely different way of presenting the CC with some being very detailed and others very brief.

More details about every course can be found in the institutional website of each department by searching for the specific course code which is rather inconvenient and time consuming. One

positive thing is that for the majority of the departments there is an English version for each course's description.

Faculty	Theology
School	Theology
Qualification Awarded	ΠΤΥΧΙΟ ΘΕΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ (Ptychio Theologias)(Degree in Theology)
Programme of Study	UPS School of Theology (2013-today)
Cycle / Level	1st / Undergraduate
Academic Year	2023 - 2024
Status	Inactive
Website	http://www.theo.auth.gr/
Contact email	info@theo.auth.gr
Calendar	URL
ECTS / Workload	One ECTS unit corresponds to 25 hours of workload.

► Presentation Options

Courses of the 1st semester

1st semester
14 classes

Code	Title	ECTS	Type
101	Ancient Greek	5	COR
104	Introduction to the Old Testament and Biblical Hebrew Language	5	COR
106	Introduction to the Study and the Methodology of Theology	4	COR
107	New Testament I: Introduction, History and Culture of the New Testament period	6	COR
109	Ecclesiastical History I	6	COR
208	Theory and methodology in the study of religion(s) of the ancient and current world	5	COR
301	Interpretation of Interpretation of the Poetical and Prophetical Books of the Old Testament from the Septuagint Text	4	COR
407	Fundamental Issues of Education Sciences	6	COR
507	Dogmatics I.: History of Orthodox Theology and Spirituality and Symbolic Theology	5	COR
2144	The theology of icons and the modern world	3	ELC
AF1	English for Theological studies I	2	FL
FA1	French Language (1st semester)	2	FL
FE1	German Language (1st semester)	2	FL
E\1	Modern Greek Language 1st semester	2	FL

Figure 20 List of available courses for the department of Theology

Best CC examples

University of Crete (UoC)

The University of Crete provides a comprehensive catalog of its courses, featuring both its local offerings and those available through the Erasmus program. By navigating to the designated Erasmus tab on the same page, students can easily explore a curated list of international study opportunities. Additionally, the platform offers insightful general statistics about the various fields of study. While lauded for its organization, a notable drawback is the necessity to visit individual

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

department websites to access detailed course information. In addition, notice some of the information is not properly translated into English and the information about programme structure and credits is not presented.

Figure 21 UoC CC page

The CC is basically a union of CCs of each department and there is information about its title, code, semester and the instructor. As shown in Figure 7, the Erasmus CC is following the same format.

University of Crete course catalog 2023-24

ΣΥΝΟΛΙΚΟΣ ΚΑΤΑΛΟΓΟΣ ΜΑΘΗΜΑΤΩΝ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟΥ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ 2023-24

Σχολή	Τμήμα	Κωδ.	Τίτλος	Τίτλος (Αγγλ.)	Ενεργό	Διδάσκοντες	Περ.
ΙΑΤΡΙΚΗ ΣΧΟΛΗ	Άσκηση και φυσική αποκατάσταση σε ασθενείς με καρδιαγγειακά νοσήματα	(M) CARDIO-101	Anatomy and physiology of cardiovascular system – Exercise physiology	Anatomy and physiology of cardiovascular system – Exercise physiology	✓	Δρακωνάκη Ελένη	(X)
		(M) CARDIO-102	Clinical evaluation of patients with cardiovascular diseases, cardiomyopathies and congenital heart diseases.	Clinical evaluation of patients with cardiovascular diseases, cardiomyopathies and congenital heart diseases.	✓	Μαρκέτου Μαρία	(X)
		(M) CARDIO-103	Ergospirometry/Cardiopulmonary exercise test	Ergospirometry/Cardiopulmonary exercise test	✓	Μαρκέτου Μαρία	(X)
		(M) CARDIO-104	Research Methods and Statistics	Research Methods and Statistics	✓	Χλουβεράκης Γρηγόρης	(X)
		(M) CARDIO-105	Diet and lifestyle in cardiac diseases	Diet and lifestyle in cardiac diseases	✓	Μαρκέτου Μαρία	(X)
	Άσκηση και φυσική αποκατάσταση σε ασθενείς με καρδιαγγειακά νοσήματα	# 5					
	ΔΠΜΣ Βιοιατρική Μηχανική	(M) BME 1	Cell Biology and Physiology	Cell Biology and Physiology	✓	Παυλόπουλος Αναστάσιος	(X)
		(M) BME 10	Molecular Diagnostics and Precision Medicine	Molecular Diagnostics and Precision Medicine	✓	Κλώντζας Μιχαήλ	(X)
		(M) BME 2	Applied anatomy	Applied anatomy	✓	Τσιτσάκης Γιάννης	(X)
		(M) BME 3	Measurement and Analysis of Bio-	Measurement and Analysis of Bio-	✓	Τσιτσάκης Γιάννης	(X)

Figure 22 . Part of the CC (School of Medicine)

ΚΑΤΑΛΟΓΟΣ ΜΑΘΗΜΑΤΩΝ Erasmus ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟΥ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ 2023-24

Σχολή	Τμήμα	Κωδ.	Τίτλος	Τίτλος (Αγγλ.)	Ενεργό	Διδάσκοντες	Περ.
ΣΧΟΛΗ ΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΩΝ ΑΓΩΓΗΣ	Resilience in Educational Contexts	(M) UOC 1005	Prevention Programs for Vulnerable Preschool and Elementary School Children	Prevention Programs for Vulnerable Preschool and Elementary School Children	✓	Ματσάπουλος Αναστάσιος, Τριλιβα Σοφία	(E)
		# 1					
		# 1					
ΣΧΟΛΗ ΘΕΤΙΚΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΚΩΝ ΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΩΝ	ΤΜΗΜΑ ΒΙΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ	(Π) ERA-1	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-3	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) BIOΛ-417	Erasmus Placement	Erasmus Placement	✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-5	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-7	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-9	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(X)
		(Π) ERA-2	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-4	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-6	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		(Π) ERA-8	Erasmus Μάθημα		✓		(XE)
		# 10					

Figure 23 Erasmus CC

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Other examples

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (UOA)

At Kapodistrian University, accessing course information proves challenging for international students due to the lack of a centralized platform. With course details scattered across various departmental websites, finding relevant information becomes time-consuming and confusing.

To simplify the process, the university should consider creating a centralized CC platform. By consolidating course information into one user-friendly interface, students, including international ones, can easily explore course offerings and make informed decisions about their academic pursuits.

In Figure 8, the CC for the Department of Economics and Political Science is displayed as an example.

— GLOBAL LIST OF COURSES OFFERED IN
— ENGLISH FOR ERASMUS/CIVIS
— National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
School of Economic and Political Sciences

<http://en.econ.uoa.gr/erasmus.html> (See here for courses discriptions only for the Department of Economics - 7 ECTS per course)

KEEP IN MIND : If you are scheduled to be registerd at the Department of Economics , you must take at least 3 courses from the Department of Economics in order to be able to proceed with your registration before the begining of the fall or spring semester . The rest of the courses can be selected from the other Departments of the School of Economics and Political Sciences

Global list of Courses offered by the Departments of School of Economics and Political Sciences

The School consists of the Departments of :

Economics Science

Political Science and Public Administration

Turkish Studies and Modern Asian Studies

Media and Communication

Ports Management and Shipping

Business Administration

Figure 24 Erasmus CC main web page of the Economic and Political Sciences department (UoA)

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

By clicking on the link, we can see information for the departments of economics and political science.

As shown in Figure 9, the catalog includes information about the course's title, ECTS, semester and tutor.

University of Patras

The University of Patras does not seem to offer a single CC and only some of the departments seem to offer an Erasmus CC online. Information about the courses of every department can be found only in the webpages of the departments, usually in the Undergraduate Studies area. In the department of Physics, it is stated as shown in Figure 10, that most of the departments create individual study programmes, with private tutoring for Erasmus students. The faculty member in charge of a course prepares a study program for the exchange students enrolled in his/her course based on English resources.

Erasmus+

Erasmus+ (2014-2020), also called Erasmus Plus, is the new EU funding program for education, training, youth and sport. The new Erasmus+ programme combines all the EU's past schemes including the Lifelong Learning Programme (Erasmus, Leonardo da Vinci, Comenius, Grundtvig), Youth in Action and five international cooperation programmes (Erasmus Mundus, Tempus, Alfa, Edulink and the programme for cooperation with industrialised countries).

The University of Patras participates in the Erasmus+ programme, and has conducted c. 200 Bilateral Agreements with higher education institutions all over Europe that facilitate the mobility of students, teaching and administrative staff. Undergraduate courses in English are available in Primary Education and in the Department of Educational Sciences and Early Childhood Education. In Master level, Departments of Civil Engineering and Chemical Engineering offer courses in English. In all other fields Erasmus students follow individual study programmes, with private tutoring. The faculty member in charge of a course prepares a study program for the exchange students enrolled in his/her course based on English resources (books, the internet etc). Students are assessed by a written exam (in English) or project(s) development and in some cases by both. There are also courses offered in German, French

Figure 25. Summary of the Erasmus+ course system of the University of Patras

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Hungary

In this chapter, we will analyse the course catalogues of the two universities most actively participating in the Erasmus+ mobility programme.

Generic examples

The Course Catalogue about to be introduced belongs to the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (referred to as **BME** from here on), an internationally acclaimed HEI of considerable size, hosting a lot of students on mobility. This type of CC is the most common nationwide. It is a collection of formatted PDF files, grouped by faculty (or other unit type) containing the list of courses available to incoming students.

Finding the Course Catalogues

The course catalogue can be found by a google search for the term “BME course catalogue erasmus”. Using these, the page¹¹ (Figure 1.) is the first hit in the google search results. If the “erasmus” keyword is not added, it takes a lot more time to find the corresponding page. The title of the page is “Academic Information”, which is rather general. The page contains - in order of appearance - links to general information, application information, application procedures and links to course catalogues by organisational units. Note the position of the scrollbar in Figure 1 to know the position of the course catalogue links inside the page.

¹ <https://kth.bme.hu/en/for-students/exchange-and-semester-abroad-students/academic-information/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

PLEASE CLICK THE NAMES OF THE FACULTIES BELOW TO SEE THEIR AVAILABLE COURSES.

FACULTY OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

Please be informed that some courses of the Faculty of Civil Engineering (especially laboratory courses) may be limited in Neptun for part-time students of other faculties to ensure the advance of the full-time students in their curriculum. MSc courses are available only for students with BSc certificate in Civil Engineering.

Timetable

FACULTY OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

The detailed course info is available in the Faculty's **Course Database**. The database is comprised of only courses belonging to the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering (including courses which are not available for Erasmus incoming students; thus, examine the course offer list first). For info about another Faculty's courses, contact the corresponding coordinator.

Please note that if you apply for the Mechanical Engineering field of study at BME, at least 70% of your credits must be chosen from **Mechanical Engineering courses**. The remaining 30% of the credits can be freely selected from other faculties' courses. If you apply for any other field of study, you can register for Mechanical Engineering courses without limit.

MSc courses are available only for students with BSc certificate in Mechanical Engineering. Please attach it to your application. Otherwise, your MSc course registrations will be cancelled without any further notice.

Students interested in a **Final Thesis project (BSc, MSc)** must fill out the **form for Final Thesis proposal**, which is followed by the student's assignment to a relevant department. **Final Thesis projects cannot be accepted without submitting the form!** Following the assignment, the **Letter of Declaration** must be filled out and sent to the Faculty Erasmus coordinator. Deadlines and further details of the procedure are published in the form's headline.

Further assistance in need can be obtained by contacting the Faculty Erasmus coordinator of GPK at erasmus_gpk@m365.bme.hu

FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE

Please note that Faculty of Architecture offers admission for 1 or 2 terms and subjects for exchange and study abroad students in its 10 term long Integrated MSc Program in Architectural Engineering training program including both BSc and MSc level subjects.

Figure 26 . Screenshot of the BME CC page from google search results

Navigating the course catalogue

This aspect means how you navigate inside the course catalogue. Filtering for criteria, searching for courses of a specific programme or with a specific subject.

The landing page² (figure 2.) is a collection of vital information for the Erasmus+ students, not limited to course catalogues. You can navigate to the course catalogue of each faculty via links provided. Clicking these, opens a course catalogue in PDF format (per faculty), that contains the available courses for the next academic year (upcoming 2 semesters 2024-2025/1, 2024-2025/2 at the time of writing).²

So, filtering is not available, courses are only grouped by faculty. Searching for a specific course or course related information is either by reading through the documents or using your browser's search function for a keyword, though that works as expected from a text finder, it will take you through the hits one-by-one regardless of where the text was found in the document.

² <https://kth.bme.hu/en/for-students/exchange-and-semester-abroad-students/academic-information/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE

Please note that Faculty of Architecture offers admission for 1 or 2 terms and subjects for exchange and study abroad students in its 10 term long Integrated MSc Program in Architectural Engineering training program including both BSc and MSc level subjects.

Please also note that you can register for courses of Architecture only if you apply for Architecture or Civil Engineering field of study at BME in your online application.

Please also note that **PROJECT TYPE COURSES** (e.g. Diploma Project, Final Project, Project Laboratory, Teamwork Project, Thesis Project, Comprehensive Design, Department Design) are **not available but** as **design subject Interdisciplinary, Project based Design F** (or **S** in the spring semester) is offered.

List of departments with codes for 'Architectural Research for Exchange Student' course but please note: This course can be taken only once a term and if you take it in the autumn term then you can take it in the spring term as well, but at another department.

FACULTY OF CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY

FACULTY OF ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND INFORMATICS

MSc courses are available only for students with BSc certificate in Electrical or Computer Engineering. Please attach it to your application otherwise your MSc course registrations will be cancelled without any further notice. Please note that there can be no exception in any case!

FACULTY OF TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING AND VEHICLE ENGINEERING

FACULTY OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

FACULTY OF NATURAL SCIENCES/COGNITIVE SCIENCES

FOREIGN LANGUAGE COURSES - CENTRE FOR MODERN LANGUAGES

Figure 27 Screenshot of a segment of the BME Course Catalogue

Content of the course catalogue

This aspect investigates what specific information is available about programmes and individual courses in the catalogue itself.

Course information is formatted as a PDF, which contains all the courses available for incoming students in an overview format (Figure 3.). Interactivity is limited to links in the PDFs for most courses on one Faculty.³

³ https://www.kth.bme.hu/document/2978/original/FCE1_24251_v1.pdf

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Subject code	Subject name			Requirement	ECTS credit
BMEEOFAS42	Field Course of Structural Geodesy			Mid-semester mark	1
Course type	Course code	Course language	Timetable information		
Laboratory	EN1	English	MON:14:15-18:00(KF27k)		
Laboratory	EN2	English	MON:14:15-18:00(KF27k)		
The main purpose of the subject is introduce the most modern techniques and methods for students in the field of state surveying and movement detection of civil engineering structures. The students apply the skills and knowledges learned in Surveying I, II and Field Course of Surveying to solve more complex structural engineering projects. Project are solved by students team. During the practices students survey some inner parts of a more levelled building, determine the geometry of axis of an about 30 m high brick chimney. Furthermore they determine the deflections of a slab and the distortions of floor. They determine the deflection of a cable bridge caused by traffic. They are introduced into the applications of photogrammetry, remote sensing and laserscanning in the area of construction engineering.					
Subject code	Subject name			Requirement	ECTS credit
BMEEOFAT41	Surveying I.			Mid-semester mark	3
Course type	Course code	Course language	Timetable information		
Laboratory	EN3	English	FRI:08:15-10:00(KF27k); FRI:08:15-10:00(KF27k)		
Laboratory	EN1	English	THU:08:15-10:00(KF27b); THU:08:15-10:00(KF27b)		
Laboratory	EN6	English	THU:10:15-12:00(KF27b); THU:10:15-12:00(KF27b)		
Laboratory	EN5	English	FRI:08:15-10:00(KF27b); FRI:08:15-10:00(KF27b)		
Lecture	EN0	English	MON:12:15-14:00(KM30)		
Surveying and Geodesy. Height systems. Optical levelling, the surveyors' level. Line levelling (procedure, field observations and processing). Systematic error sources of levelling, the two-peg-test. Line levelling, detail point levelling. Height observations for horizontal layouts. Horizontal positioning observations. Angular observations and the theodolite. Calibration procedure of the theodolite. Measuring with the theodolites: set up, sighting, horizontal and vertical angular observations, systematic error sources. The computation of the mean direction and the zenith angle. Centring excentric observations. Trigonometric heighting. Distance observations: corrections, reductions. Physical methods of distance measurements. Electrooptical Distance Meters. Processing distance observations. Plane surveying. Computation of horizontal coordinates on the projection grid. Orientation of the horizontal circle. Intersections.					

Figure 28 . Screenshot of a segment of BME Course Information PDFs

The Course Catalogue contains the following information about the individual courses:

Subject code: The identifier of the course

Subject name: Course title

Requirement: Requirements for enrolling in the course

ECTS credits

Course type: Laboratory / Lecture / Practice

Course code: the subcode of the course instance

Course language: Language of instruction

Timetable information: When is the course instance held (weekday, starting time, ending time)

Programme information is not accessible directly from the course catalogue.

Availability of other related information

This aspect covers the availability and accessibility of other information related to going on mobility (as an incoming student) to the target HEI.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The analysed page - that also contains the course catalogue - reveals information related to taking part in the Erasmus+ mobility programme. You can easily find the following important data:

- General information: Welcome letter, Welcome presentation, Recent newsletters issued, Academic calendar for the next two semesters and a Campus map
- Application information: Application periods, nomination information
- Application procedure: For EU and non-EU students

Best CC example

The next Course Catalogue to be reviewed belongs to Eötvös Loránd University (referred to as **ELTE** from here on). This CC is a good example of an interactive, filterable, searchable system that contains course and programme information in a navigable web page format.

Finding the Course Catalogue

This aspect as the title suggests means how easy it is to find the course catalogue on the internet via google search.

The course catalogue page⁴ of one of the faculties in the HEI is the second hit in a google search using the "ELTE course catalogue" search term. Arriving on the resulting page, the title clearly states the purpose of the page⁴ "COURSE CATALOGUE FOR INCOMING ERASMUS STUDENTS", there is a clear indication of where to click to find the catalogue for the whole Institution showing all the courses offered by all the organisational units. Even if you check the first result in the google search, you can get to a Course Catalogue in four clicks.

⁴ <https://btk.elte.hu/en/content/course-catalogue-for-incoming-erasmus-students.t.3543?m=261>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Dear Incoming Students,

Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE) intends to start the autumn semester of the academic year of 2024/25 with personal attendance.

ELTE strongly recommends for all University Citizens and university applicants to take the opportunity to be vaccinated.

We recommend you consider your mobility semester on the basis of the published course catalogues.

Incoming Erasmus students should choose courses from these lists and from the relevant institute/department they are nominated to. If you wish to register for courses offered by an other institute/department please always consult the academic (Institutional/departmental) coordinators before (see list below).

You will already be aware that our agreements are specific to the subject areas in which they are set up and are based upon the specific request of individual disciplines. Students must discuss their programme of study with the **academic coordinators** concerned in order for them to see if the study programme of their preference can be duly executed.

Your Learning Agreement should be signed by your academic coordinator as "Responsible Person at Host University".

[Please find our academic coordinators here.](#)

[Please find our courses for international guest/part time students here.](#)

Figure 29 Screenshot of the ELTE CC page from google search results

Navigating the course catalogues

This aspect means how you navigate inside the course catalogue. Filtering for criteria, searching for courses from a specific programme or with a specific subject.

On the ELTE International Course Catalogue page⁵, you can filter by the following criteria:

- Faculty (narrows Programme choices when picked)
- Programme
- Semester (1st or 2nd in general)
- Active semesters with the choices:
 - Published: Means the course is being held or is planned in the upcoming two semesters
 - Is held in the active semester (2023-2024/2 at the time of writing)
 - Is held in the next semester (2024-2025/1 at the time of writing)

5

<https://neptun.elte.hu/MobilityCourses?Faculty=BTK&Programme=&AcademicTerm=&Published=&SearchText=>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Searching through the individual courses happens via type-in text box without auto-complete.

Figure 30 Screenshot of the ELTE Course Catalogue filtering and searching systems

Content of the course catalogue

This aspect investigates what specific information is available about programmes and individual courses in the catalogue itself.

There are different views in the course catalogue of ELTE the user can access. The list view (Figure 5.) contains an expandable overview (Figure 6.), embedded in the list of courses matching the filtered criteria and the details view (Figure 7.), opened by clicking on the details button in the list of courses. We will list the information available in these views.

List view

Courses

...	Title (code)	Usual [?]	Published [?]	ECTS [?]	Lang.	...
▶	Accounting I. (GT124AN104EN)	Autumn [?]	2023/24/2	6	en	☰
▶	Accounting II. (GT124AN206EN)	Spring [?]	2023/24/2	3	en	☰
▶	Analysis and Controlling (GT124AN314EN)	Autumn [?]	2023/24/2	6	en	☰
▶	Argumentation (GT121AN306EN)	Autumn [?]	2023/24/2	3	en	☰

Figure 31 Screenshot of the list view in ELTE's course catalogue

The list view contains all the user search results. The table below displays the course information visible in this view.

Table 3 List of course information available on the list view

Course information	List view (Yes / No)	Overview (Yes / No)	Details view (Yes / No)
Course title and code	Yes	Yes	Yes
Usual (semester)	Yes	Yes	Yes

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Published (active)	Yes	Yes	Yes
ECTS credits	Yes	Yes	Yes
Language of instruction	Yes	Yes	Yes

Overview

Accounting I. (GTI24AN104EN)		Autumn	2023/24/2	6	en
Faculty	Faculty of Economics				
Organization	GTK Department of Finance and Accounting				
Code	GTI24AN104EN				
Title	Accounting I.				
Learning outcomes	This is a first introductory course in accounting for students with no previous background in accounting or business. The primary objective of the course is to develop the students' understanding and knowledge of the underlying principles and concepts relating to financial accounting including the double-entry bookkeeping system and the preparation of basic financial statements. A specific aim is to use financial accounting information for decision-making purposes and to evaluate the financial position and performance of business entities.				
Course content	Introduction into Accounting, The regulatory framework of accounting, the content of the annual report, financial statements Sources, records and books of prime entry Accounting conventions, dual nature of economic transactions Ledger accounts and double entry From trial balance to financial statements Inventory valuation (recognition of inventory, lower of cost and NRV, FIFO, AVCO) Sales tax and other taxes Tangible non-current assets (initial recognition, depreciation, disposal) Accruals and prepayments Provisions and contingencies, events after the reporting period Irrecoverable debts and allowances Preparation of financial statements of companies Cash Flow Statement ...				
Assessment method	The general examination and assessment requirements of the courses offered by the Faculty of Economics are available at: https://eltehu.sharepoint.com/sites/GTKstudents/SitePages/The_principles_and_ground_rules.aspx				
Bibliography	Presentations and notes of lectures and seminars Frank Wood's: Business Accounting Vol. 1, 13th Edition, Pearson Education 2015 Financial accounting Study Text, BPP Learning Media 2016 Practical assignments available from the course's Moodle profile				

[Details](#)

Figure 32 Screenshot of the overview in ELTE's course catalogue

The overview embedded and expandable without leaving the list view contains the following information in addition to the ones in the list view:

Table 4 List of course information available on the overview

Course information	List view (Yes / No)	Overview (Yes / No)	Details view (Yes / No)
Faculty	No	Yes	Yes

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Organisation	No	Yes	Yes
Learning outcomes	No	Yes	Yes
Course content	No	Yes	Yes
Assessment method	No	Yes	Yes
Bibliography	No	Yes	Yes

Details view

Details view of a course (individual educational component)

Faculty	Faculty of Economics
Organization	GTK Department of Finance and Accounting
Code	GTI24AN104EN
Title	Accounting I.
Usual semester	Autumn
Published semester 	2023/24/2
ECTS 	6
Language	en
Learning outcomes	This is a first introductory course in accounting for students with no previous background in accounting or business. The primary objective of the course is to develop the students' understanding and knowledge of the underlying principles and concepts relating to financial accounting including the double-entry bookkeeping system and the preparation of basic financial statements. A specific aim is to use financial accounting information for decision-making purposes and to evaluate the financial position and performance of business entities.
Course content	Introduction into Accounting, The regulatory framework of accounting, the content of the annual report, financial statements Sources, records and books of prime entry Accounting conventions, dual nature of economic transactions Ledger accounts and double entry From trial balance to financial statements Inventory valuation (recognition of inventory, lower of cost and NRV, FIFO, AVCO) Sales tax and other taxes Tangible non-current assets (initial recognition, depreciation, disposal) Accruals and prepayments Provisions and contingencies, events after the reporting period Irrecoverable debts and allowances Preparation of financial statements of companies Cash Flow Statement Financial Statement analysis
Assessment method	The general examination and assessment requirements of the courses offered by the Faculty of Economics are available at: https://eltehu.sharepoint.com/sites/GTKstudents/SitePages/The_principles_and_ground_rules.aspx
Bibliography	Presentations and notes of lectures and seminars Frank Wood's: Business Accounting Vol. 1, 13th Edition, Pearson Education 2015 Financial accounting Study Text, BPP Learning Media 2016 Practical assignments available from the course's Moodle profile

Programmes of the course

Title (code)	Lang.	Level	...		
Erasmus Programme (GTK-ERASMUS-NXXX)	hu				
Finance and Accounting (GTK-PS-NBEN)	en	6	Mandatory		
International Business Economics (GTK-NG-NBEN)	en	6	Mandatory	1/4	
International Business Economics (GTK-NG8-NBEN)	en	6	Mandatory	1/4	

[Back](#)

Figure 33 Screenshot of the details view in ELTE's course catalogue

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The details view is a separate page for an individual course. It is accessible from the list view by clicking the details button. This view is practically the same as the overview, except it lists all the programmes, containing the specific course. From the list of programmes, it is possible to navigate to the main page of the course catalogue with the filters set to the programme clicked.

Table 5 List of course information available on the details view

Course information	List view (Yes / No)	Overview (Yes / No)	Details view (Yes / No)
Programmes of the Course	No	No	Yes

Availability of other related information

This aspect covers the availability and accessibility of other information related to going on mobility (as an incoming student) to the target HEI.

The course catalogue page does not contain any information related to going on mobility as an incoming student. The user has to perform at least one additional search. The first hit of the google search for the terms "elte erasmus information" however is the general information page of the Institution. The resulting page contains information about:

- General Information about the Erasmus+ programme, including it's benefits
- Who is eligible to apply?
- How to apply?
- Nomination and application deadlines
- Special needs support
- Information for foreign students already enrolled in a full-degree programme at ELTE
- Links to the following pages and contacts:
 - Contact to the Institutional Erasmus coordinator
 - Contact page of the facultyErasmus coordinators
 - Link to a page with a vast collection of practical information for international students
 - Link to a list of degree-programmes available by - among other criteria - language
 - Link to the Course Catalogue analysed above

A wider picture

There are currently 55 ECHE holders in the country. These range from tiny HEIs to internationally renowned Universities of considerable size. To get a wider view on the state of CCs in the country, we will attempt to find and take a brief look at the CCs of the 3 universities with the most outgoing students⁶ (see rankings source later) and the 4 - excluding the ones already in the document - highest rated universities in the country according to eduline.hu's article⁷. The 2 rankings are the following:

Universities with the most outgoing students:

- Eötvös Loránd University (already analysed)
- Budapest University of Technology and Economics (already analysed)
- Budapest Metropolitan University (see number 1. below)

Highest ranked universities in the country:

1. Eötvös Loránd University (already analysed)
2. University of Szeged (see number 2. below)
3. Budapest University of Technology and Economics (already analysed)
4. University of Debrecen (see number 3. below)
5. Semmelweis University (see number 4. below)
6. Budapest Corvinus University (see number 5. below)

An important sidenote: As you might know, Hungary was recently penalised for the financing structure of some of its universities, because they are managed by foundations tied closely to the government, but as a result of this organisational structure their finances are not transparent enough according to EU standards. Without forming an opinion, this objectively results in a lot of large HEIs being banned from sending students and staff members on mobilities from the beginning of the 2024/2025 academic year. Ongoing agreements and the ones taking place in the 2023/2024 academic year are not affected.

1. Budapest Metropolitan University

This HEI has the same type of CC as BME, the landing page⁸ for incoming Erasmus students contains sufficient information to start your application as an incoming student and a collection of PDF⁹ documents with the lists of the courses available per module (similar to a faculty in this specific case).

2. University of Szeged - HU SZEGED01

Contextual information:

This HEI is considered large in the country. It is the home of 22.000 students out of which more than 4.000 are international.

⁶ <https://www.vg.hu/vilaggazdasag-magyar-gazdasag/2023/08/a-nem-modellvalto-egyetemen-terjes-a-nyugalom-erasmus-ugyben-sot-meg-kis-haszon-is-kinezhet-a-jovo-evi-felveteliken>

⁷ https://eduline.hu/felsooktatasi/20230720_HVG_felspoktatasi_rangsor_2023

⁸ <https://www.metubudapest.hu/incoming-exchange-students>

⁹ <https://www.metubudapest.hu/upload/0f3a3bf68d50209765d78c2c71a914291454ece9.pdf>

The landing page of Incoming Erasmus students¹⁰ is the first hit of the google search with the terms “university of szeged erasmus incoming” contains a lot of information, the paragraphs are outdated and disorganised. The essential documents and information can be found by browsing through the left side menu, but it takes a lot of clicking and some patience.

Once managing to find the course catalogue, we will find a collection of links per faculty to the courses offered. Each link leads to the webpages of the corresponding faculty. Course information is either presented as a list or a downloadable document.

3. University of Debrecen - HU DEBRECE01

Contextual information:

This HEI is (hopefully temporarily) banned from the 2024/2025 academic year from incoming and outgoing mobilities.

Considering this HEI is not located in the capital, its size is relatively large in the country. It is the home of 27.000 students of which 4.000 are international.

Applying the same logic as before, the first hit of a google search for “University of Debrecen erasmus incoming” is the landing page¹¹ for incoming mobility information. Practical information could be found easily, but it is only accessible after authentication, so it is not viewable for guests.

The course catalogue¹² takes a few clicks to navigate to, rather easy to find, but the course information provided only contains a list of titles grouped by degree level without any access to additional information.

4. Semmelweis University

Contextual information:

This HEI is an internationally acknowledged centre for healthcare education.

It has almost 16.000 students actively enrolled.

The landing page¹³ dedicated to incoming Erasmus students is the first hit of the google search for “semmelweis university erasmus incoming”. It contains links to general information (application details, forms, learning agreement documents) by faculty and an 830 page long document embedded in a PDF viewer with information about apparently the HEI itself. Extremely detailed course information¹⁴ is contained therein, but it takes time and patience to find the corresponding pages. Should you want to see it - it is worth checking - , there is a great example of a course description starting on page 79 (by the document

¹⁰ <http://www2.u-szeged.hu/erasmus/eindex.html>

¹¹ <https://internationaloffice.unideb.hu/en/incoming-students>

¹² <https://internationaloffice.unideb.hu/node/295>

¹³ <https://semmelweis.hu/erasmus/en/2043-2/>

¹⁴ https://semmelweis.hu/erasmus/files/2023/11/semmelweis_kiado_file_1694088280.pdf

paper), page 81 according to the PDF page count. Programme information is also available at the beginning of each faculty chapter. In order to be handleable, the document should be downloaded.

This is a prime example of a well composed and very detailed course catalogue with very poor handling and practically no navigation.

5. Budapest Corvinus University - HU BUDAPES03

Contextual information:

- One of the most famous universities nationally (same renown as ELTE and BME). Specialised mainly in Economy and related fields.
- Currently has 10.000 students, out of which 2.000 are international.

The landing page¹⁵ intended for Incoming Erasmus students is the first hit of the google search for the terms "budapest corvinus university incoming erasmus". It contains links to general information as usual, though application deadlines are not displayed. The direct links to the course catalogue are on the page.

The catalogue itself is a collection of structured PDF files (link to an example in the footnote¹⁶), grouped by level (BA/BSc, MA/MSc) and semester (spring or fall). It contains limited information about the individual educational components themselves, namely course identification code, course title and ECTS credits. No organisational unit, faculty or degree programme information is displayed.

¹⁵ <https://www.uni-corvinus.hu/ind/international-and-administrative-student-services/incoming-exchange-student/?lang=en>

¹⁶ https://www.uni-corvinus.hu/contents/uploads/2023/12/NEW-FINAL_Corvinus-Erasmus-BSC-course-list-2024-spring.eed.pdf

Portugal

In Portugal, typically higher education institutions provide course catalogues. These catalogues list all the available courses offered by the institution, including detailed information about each course such as course descriptions, prerequisites, credit hours, and schedules. Whether it is a university, polytechnic institute, or another type of higher education institution, everyone can typically access these catalogues to make informed decisions about the institution's course offering.

Moreover, the Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES)¹⁷, a central service of the Ministry of Education and Science whose mission is to ensure the design, implementation and coordination of the policies that fall within the scope of higher education. Their website offers comprehensive information on various aspects of higher education and a course choosing assistant, which is an online service that includes course catalogues of public and private universities and polytechnics.

Table 1 presents a list of higher education institutions in Portugal along with information regarding their Course Catalogues (CCs). This list is deemed representative of the overall situation in the country. This list includes very similar CC solutions, with the representation of three centenary universities in Portugal (U.Porto, ULisboa and UC), as well as three other prominent institutions that rank among the largest in higher education in the country (IPP, UMinho and UA).

These institutions offer a diverse range of academic programs, including bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees, as well as vocational and technical courses. They play a crucial role in shaping Portugal's higher education landscape and contributing to the country's academic and research achievements.

Table 6 List of main CCs in Portugal

Institution	CC Web address	Generic information	Resources and Services	Programmes	Individual Educational Components
Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES)	https://www.dges.gov.pt/guias/indmain.asp	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Porto (Universidade do Porto – U.PORTO)	https://www.up.pt/portal/en/study/bachelors-and-integrated-	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available

¹⁷ DGES website: <https://www.dges.gov.pt/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

	masters-degrees/courses/				
Polytechnic Institute of Porto (Instituto Politécnico de Porto – IPP)	https://www.ippp.pt/ensino/cursos	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Lisbon (Universidade de Lisboa – ULisboa)	https://www.ulisboa.pt/en/info/programmes-0	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Coimbra (Universidade de Coimbra – UC)	https://www.ucp.pt/en/ects/catalogo/	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Minho (Universidade do Minho – UMinho)	https://www.uminho.pt/PT/ensino/oferta-educativa/Cursos-Conferentes-a-Grau/Paginas/Licenciaturas-e-Mestrados-Integrados.aspx	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
University of Aveiro (Universidade de Aveiro – UA)	https://www.ua.pt/en/course-types	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available

Generic examples

Instituto Politécnico de Porto – IPP (Polytechnic Institute of Porto)

The Polytechnic Institute of Porto (IPP) does not have a proper Course Catalogue (CC), but the information of the CC can be found partially on the institutional website¹⁸ and fully on each of the 8 school's websites that belong to the IPP. The information is available on the institutional website in the "EDUCATION" item, under "COURSES" (Figure 1). The website is available in Portuguese and English.

Figure 34 IPP website menu

¹⁸ IPP website: <https://www.ipp.pt/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Each school within IPP showcases their course offerings on their respective websites. In the case of the School of Engineering (ISEP), it has a distinct website design compared to the Polytechnic website, featuring its programs under the "STUDY" section (Figure 2).

Figure 35 ISEP website course information

As for the course information on the IPP website is provided in a simplified way and not all courses appear at once, as it is shown in Figure 3, including data about: the school, the credits, the course cycle and the study scheme.

Figure 36 . ISEP courses

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The more detailed information about the course are links to other pages, such as, a short summary, the coordinator, the study plan with the list of the courses and respective ects, career opportunities and information regarding the access (see Figure 4). Therefore, key information is not provided directly.

The screenshot shows a web page for the 'AUTOMOTIVE ENGINEERING' course at ISEP. The page includes a navigation menu, a search icon, and the university logo 'P.PORTO'. The breadcrumb trail is 'home > education > courses > undergraduate degrees > isep > automotive engineering'. The main heading is 'AUTOMOTIVE ENGINEERING' with a 'Ouvrir' button. Below this is a summary: 'BSc: 3 years (180 ECTS units) Automotive Engineering study and develops safer, comfortable and efficient vehicles. Geared towards technical innovation, it seeks solutions to increase performances and ...'. There are four tabs: 'PRESENTATION', 'STUDY PLANS', 'CAREER OPPORTUNITIES', and 'ACCESS'. The 'PRESENTATION' tab is active, showing a detailed description of the course, its goals, and the curriculum. Below the description, there is a 'Studies scheme' section with details like 'Full-time', 'Course coordinator: Fernando José Ferreira', 'DGES Record Number: 9936', and 'Date: 01/01/2001'.

Figure 37 ISEP course description

As discussed before, another important thing is this information can also be provided by each school website. Therefore, all the programmes provided by the same faculty or school are provided together. Nevertheless, a broader view of the whole university programmes is not offered at this level.

The IPP website contains more of the information required by the ECTS Users' Guide, but the information is dispersed in several different sections and it is not provided in an attractive and homogeneous way. The information on programmes is rather scarce and most of the sections contain links to other sites not directly related or well-integrated with the CC.

The information on courses is provided in a different site and some of the translations are not available. Users may get lost easily and the general learning experience could be improved in many ways.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Universidade de Lisboa - ULisboa (University of Lisbon)

The University of Lisbon (ULisboa) doesn't have a dedicated course catalogue but offers comprehensive educational program information on its official website¹⁹. This information can be accessed through the main menu, under the "STUDY" item and then "PROGRAMMES". (Figure 5)

Figure 38 ULisboa website menu

Upon choosing "PROGRAMMES," users are directed to a page presenting a structured table. On the left side of the table, schools are listed, while on the right, the associated programs (Figure 6). This layout demonstrates intuitiveness and organisation, simplifying the process for users to explore the array of programs offered by the various schools.

¹⁹ ULisboa website: <https://www.ulisboa.pt/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

About Us University Schools Social Services

U LISBOA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA Study Research and Innovation International Life at ULisboa

SCHOOL	PROGRAMME
Lisbon School of Architecture	Design General Studies Fashion Design
Faculty of Fine Arts	Multimedia Art Sciences of Art and Heritage Drawing Communication Design Equipment Design Sculpture Painting General Studies
Faculty of Sciences	Biology Biochemistry Biomedical Engineering and Biophysics Energy and Environment Engineering Engineering Physics Geospatial Engineering Informatics Engineering Applied Statistics Physics Geology Mathematics Applied Mathematics Meteorology, Oceanography and Geophysics Chemistry Technological Chemistry Information Technology General Studies Environmental Engineering (ULisboa and SHU)
Faculty of Law	Law Law European Studies General Studies
Faculty of Pharmacy	Nutritional Sciences
School of Arts and Humanities	Archaeology

ULisboa presents program profiles with key features such as credit requirements, program structure, coordinators, summaries, teaching plans, admission processes, career opportunities, and mobility options. Course information is provided in a standardised format, including course title, academic year, credits, prerequisites, department, instructors, course description, learning outcomes, teaching methods, assessment criteria, and additional resources. It also provides a link to the school webpage that offers the programme, with different alumni testimonials.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

ECONOMICS

<p>Degree BSc - Licenciatura's Degree School ISEG - Lisbon School of Economics & Management</p>	<p>Time period Day time Duration 6 ECTS 180 Language PT</p>	<p>Programme webpage aquila.iseg.ulisboa.pt Data de Acreditação A3ES 06/17/2022 Prazo de Acreditação A3ES 6 anos Deliberação A3ES Official Portuguese Code (DGES) Number R/A-Ef 2111/2011 Official Portuguese Code (DGES) Registration Date 03/18/2011</p>
---	---	--

The Degree in Economics from ISEG prepares its students to respond effectively and efficiently to the demands and challenges of the national and international labor market.

CAREER PROSPECTS

ISEG graduates leave university prepared to cope with the demands of the national and international job market. This is confirmed by the results of the survey that is regularly carried out with recent ISEG graduates, which indicate a rapid and effective integration into working life, as about 35% of students are offered a job before they graduate, with a 90% level of employment 6 months after graduating. Priority is always given at ISEG to an education aimed at placing graduates in the job market, providing students with the most appropriate skills for carrying out their activity in a variety of career opportunities. ISEG graduates find jobs in the main sectors of the economic, financial, and business worlds, particularly in the following professions: Banking Insurance Auditing and consulting International economic and financial organisations Management of industrial and service companies National or local government Study centres, teaching, and research

NATIONAL ADMISSION 2024/25

Vacancies 138
National Admission Exams
Um dos seguintes conjuntos: 19 Matemática A ou 18 Português + 19 Matemática A ou 04 Economia + 19 Matemática A
Minimum Grades - Applications 100
National Admission Exams 95
Admissions for 2023/24

Grade of the last student admitted – 1st phase 162.00
Grade of the last student admitted – 2nd phase 164.30

Fee - 1st year (indicative) 697.00€
Fee - remaining years (indicative) 697.00€

INTERNATIONAL ACCESS

Vacancies for International Students 10
Fee - 1st year (indicative) 4500,00€
Fee - remaining years (indicative) 4500,00€
On-line application for the Special Admission Contest www.iseg.ulisboa.pt

Universidade do Minho – UMinho (University of Minho)

The University of Minho (UMinho) does not have a dedicated course catalogue but offers comprehensive educational program information on its official website²⁰ and also in pdf format,

²⁰ UMinho website: <https://www.uminho.pt/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

both in Portuguese and English. This information can be accessed through the main menu, under the "Education" and "INCOME STUDENTS" tabs.

After that, the user must select the "Educational Offer" section, which presents comprehensive information on the bachelor's, master's, and PhD degrees. It is possible to refine the search by filtering courses according to scientific areas, study regime (such as after working hours, daytime, or mixed schedules), specific departments or schools within the university (referred to as units), or by directly searching for the desired course. This filtering system significantly improves user experience, enabling individuals to swiftly discover programs that align with their interests and requirements. (Figure 6).

The screenshot displays the UMinho website's educational offer page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the UMinho logo, social media icons, and a search bar. Below the navigation bar, a breadcrumb trail reads: EN > Education > Educational offer > Degree Conferring Courses > Bachelors and Integrated Masters. The main heading is "Bachelors and Integrated Masters". A disclaimer states: "The information contained in these pages does not dispense consultation of official documents." To the right, there is a dropdown menu for the academic year, currently set to "2024/2025". Below the disclaimer, there are three filter dropdown menus: "Scientific Area...", "Regime...", and "Unit...". A search bar with a magnifying glass icon and the text "Search..." is also present. On the right side, there is a vertical list of degree types: "Degree Conferring Courses", "Bachelors and Integrated Masters" (highlighted in red), "PhD degrees", and "Masters degrees". The main content area lists several degree programs, each with a circular icon containing a cross: Bachelor in Accounting, Bachelor in Aerospace Engineering, Bachelor in Applied Biology, Bachelor in Applied Languages, Bachelor in Applied Statistics, Bachelor in Archaeology, Bachelor in Basic Education, and Bachelor in Biochemistry.

Figure 39 UMinho educational offer page.

Users can then navigate to the "Degree Conferring Courses" section, where they will find a comprehensive list of available programs. Each program listed has its own detailed page, offering specific information such as course structure, objectives, admission requirements, study plan including the respective units and corresponding ECTS credits, as well as contact information (refer to Figure 7).

Accounting (Bachelor)

2024/2025

[Back](#)

The information contained in these pages does not dispense consultation of official documents.

[General](#) [Access](#) [Study Plan](#) [Assessment/Accreditation](#)

Degree Conferring Courses

Bachelors and Integrated Masters

PhD degrees

Masters degrees

General

Academic degree: Bachelor (Bologna 1st cycle degree)
ECTS: 180
Duration: 6 curricular semesters
Regime: Daytime
Place: Gualtar Campus, Braga (UM)
Main Scientific area: Accounting Management

Contacts

Course Director
 Ana Alexandra Ramos Carla Pereira ✉
 aalexandra@eeeg.uminho.pt
 Tel: 253601945

Mobility Academic Coordinator
 Maria Emilia Pereira Fernandes ✉
 mifermandes@eeeg.uminho.pt
 Tel: 253604510 ext.601941

School of Economics and Management
 Campus de Gualtar
 4710 - 057 Braga
 Tel: +351 253604510 Fax: +351 253601380
 E-Mail: pedagogico@eeeg.uminho.pt
 URL: http://www.eeeg.uminho.pt

Access to higher education

This course provides the technical and scientific capacity to access the courses of the second cycle (Master)

Figure 40 . UMinho Course description

UMinho distinguishes itself by providing a filter tool that its counterparts lack. Nonetheless, pertinent information is scattered across various sections of the website, complicating the search for specific details. Enhancements in integration are necessary to streamline access to information.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Best CC examples

Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES) course assistant

Prospective students can find detailed guidance on the admission process, including application deadlines, entry requirements, and application procedures for different universities and courses. This information is invaluable for those planning to pursue undergraduate or postgraduate studies in Portugal

Moreover, the platform provides extensive details about the diverse range of degree programs offered by universities and other higher education institutions across Portugal (Figure 8). From undergraduate courses to specialised postgraduate studies, visitors can explore the academic opportunities available to them. This comprehensive overview helps students make informed decisions about their educational paths.

DGES
Direção-Geral do Ensino Superior

DGES NOTÍCIAS EVENTOS CONTACTOS

Guia das Provas de Ingresso | Índices de Cursos

Índices de Cursos

Nesta secção poderás consultar os pares instituição/curso organizados por diversos critérios.

Por área de estudos e nome do curso

- Escolhendo uma área de estudos podes ver os cursos nela classificados;
- Escolhendo um curso poderás verificar em que instituições é lecionado;

Por nome do curso e instituições onde é lecionado

- Escolhendo um par instituição/curso é apresentada a página de detalhe do par;

Por distrito e instituição

- Escolhendo um distrito podes ver as instituições nele localizadas;

Por instituição e curso

- Escolhendo um par instituição/curso é apresentada a página de detalhe do par.

Assistente de escolha de curso

- Definindo diversos critérios de pesquisa são apresentados os pares instituição/curso que os satisfazem.

A informação apresentada inclui:

- Pares instituição/curso do ensino superior público, objeto de **concurso nacional** e objeto de **concurso local**:
A informação apresentada foi retirada do Guia das Provas de Ingresso 2024 - Ensino Superior Público:
[Versão em PDF](#)
- Pares instituição/curso do ensino superior privado, objeto de **concurso institucional**:
A informação apresentada foi retirada do Guia das Provas de Ingresso 2024 - Ensino Superior Privado:
[Versão em PDF](#)

Provas de Ingresso a Realizar

- As provas de ingresso para a candidatura à matrícula e inscrição no ensino superior no ano letivo de 2024/2025 concretizam-se através dos exames nacionais do ensino secundário.
- As provas de ingresso a realizar para a candidatura a cada curso, em cada instituição de ensino superior, são fixadas por cada instituição de ensino superior.
- Para saber quais os exames nacionais do ensino secundário que podem ser utilizados como provas de ingresso, deves consultar a Tabela B constante do [Guia Geral de Exames](#), com as instruções para a inscrição para os exames nacionais do ensino secundário.
- Nas páginas de detalhe dos cursos, encontras, para cada instituição e curso de ensino superior, as provas de ingresso que serão exigidas para a sua candidatura à matrícula e inscrição em 2024.

Figure 41 . DGES course assistant

Upon clicking on a specific degree, users are directed to a new page containing detailed information about the respective institution or course (Figure 9). Furthermore, the website serves as a repository of statistical data and information related to higher education in Portugal. Users can access enrolment figures, graduation rates, academic performance metrics, and other relevant statistics.

Engenharia Informática
Instituto Politécnico do Porto - Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto

Guia das Provas de Ingresso de 2024 - Detalhe de Curso

Endereço e Contactos da Instituição

Rua Dr. António Bernardino de
Almeida, 431
4249-015 PORTO
[Mapa](#)

Tel: 228340500
Fax: 228321159
<http://www.isep.ipp.pt>
info-sa@isep.ipp.pt

Características do par Instituição/Curso

Código: 3135/9119
Grau: Licenciatura - 1º ciclo
Área CNAEF: 523 Eletrónica e Automação
Duração: 6 Semestres
ECTS: 180
Tipo de Ensino: Ensino Superior Público Politécnico
Concurso: Nacional

A informação sobre a abertura ou não de vagas neste par instituição/curso no ano letivo de 2024-2025 será divulgada aqui antes da abertura do concurso.

Provas de Ingresso

Candidatura de 2024:

19 Matemática A

Candidatura de 2025:

Um dos seguintes conjuntos:
19 Matemática A
18 Português
ou
07 Física e Química
19 Matemática A

Dados Estatísticos de Candidaturas Anteriores

	2021		2022		2023	
	1ª Fase	2ª Fase	1ª Fase	2ª Fase	1ª Fase	2ª Fase
Vagas	200	10	200	5	201	3
Candidatos						
Candidatos	1061	202	1459	271	1310	253
do Sexo Feminino	132	19	206	32	217	20
do Sexo Masculino	929	183	1253	239	1093	233
em 1ª Opção	382	107	532	151	500	161
Colocados						
Colocados	200	14	201	10	201	8
do Sexo Feminino	31	2	32	6	40	0
do Sexo Masculino	169	12	169	4	161	8
em 1ª Opção	130	8	108	6	132	5
Médias dos Colocados						
Nota de Candidatura	164,5	169,4	171,4	179,0	171,4	168,4
Provas de Ingresso	149,3	167,8	164,6	177,5	160,1	166,0
Notas do 12º Ano	172,7	170,2	175,0	179,8	177,5	169,6
Notas do 11º Ano	172,7	170,2	175,0	179,8	177,5	169,6
Nota de Candidatura do Último Colocado pelo Contingente Geral	156,8	163,1	166,4	174,3	165,1	171,9
Informação Adicional Sobre Candidatos e Colocados	PDF					

Outras Informações

Informação estatística sobre o curso

(Vai ser direcionado para a Direção-Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência)

Informação sobre a avaliação e acreditação deste curso

(Vai ser direcionado para a Agência de Avaliação e Acreditação do Ensino Superior)

Figure 42 Information about the Institution/Course

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

This data not only provides insights into the state of higher education but also aids policymakers and educational stakeholders in making informed decisions and implementing effective strategies. Overall, the DGES platform plays a pivotal role in promoting transparency, accessibility, and excellence in higher education in Portugal. Its wealth of information and resources cater to the needs of students, educators, policymakers, and other stakeholders. However, it is worth noting that while the platform offers extensive support, the course assistance is exclusively provided in Portuguese. Additionally, users seeking to consult the course study plan must do so on the institution's website.

Universidade do Porto – U.Porto (University of Porto)

The U.Porto website²¹ offers a convenient feature under the "STUDY" tab, providing a comprehensive list of courses across different academic cycles. What makes this tool particularly noteworthy is its dual search functionality, allowing users to explore courses either by faculty or alphabetically (Figure 10). This can be particularly helpful for prospective students who are researching different programs or for current students who are planning their course schedules.

The screenshot shows the U.Porto website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'About the University' and 'Faculties' dropdowns, and social media icons. The main header includes the 'U.PORTO' logo and 'UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO' text. A secondary navigation bar contains 'STUDY', 'RESEARCH', 'INNOVATE', 'LIVE', 'EXPLORE', and a search bar. On the left, a 'STUDY' dropdown menu is open, showing options like 'Bachelor's and Integrated Master's Degrees', 'List of Courses', 'Applications and Admissions', etc. The main content area is titled 'List of Courses' and includes a paragraph about the university's offerings. Below this, there are two buttons: 'Courses by Faculty' (highlighted) and 'Courses from A to Z'. Under 'Courses by Faculty', there is a search bar with 'All' and a plus sign. Below the search bar, there are two sections: 'Faculty of Architecture' with a sub-item 'Integrated Master in Architecture', and 'Faculty of Fine Arts' with a sub-item 'First Degree in Communication Design'.

Figure 43 . U.Porto List of Courses

²¹ U.Porto website: <https://up.pt/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

When a course is selected, users are redirected to another page where various details are provided. These include a concise description of the course, potential career prospects, the language of instruction, duration, ECTS credits, and the latest admission grade. Additionally, there's a "Learn More" button that directs individuals to another page for further information (Figure 11).

The screenshot displays a web interface for U.Porto. On the left is a navigation menu under the heading 'STUDY', with 'Bachelor's and Integrated Master's Degrees' selected. The main content area features the title 'Bachelor's and Integrated Master's Degrees' and 'List of Courses'. A button labeled 'Go back to the Course List' is visible. The main section is titled 'First Degree in Applied Languages' and includes a detailed description of the program, 'Job Opportunities' (listing professions like Translation and Management), and a sidebar with course specifics. The sidebar details include:

- Where:** Faculty of Arts
- Type of Course:** First Degree
- Duration:** 6 Semesters / 180.0 ECTS
- Vacancies*:** 100
- Mark of the last classified*:** 1st Phase 172.4, 2nd Phase 170.8, 3rd Phase 172.6
- Language:** Portuguese
- Annual Tuition Fee (Full Tuition Fee):** National: 697.00€, International: 3500.00€, CPLP International: 1925.00€

 A 'Learn more' button is located at the bottom of the sidebar.

Figure 44 U.Porto degree specifics

Upon selecting a course, users are directed to the faculty's website that offers the selected course. Here, users can access more comprehensive information including general details, study plans, certificates, main scientific areas, and contact information (Figure 12). This allows individuals to delve deeper into the specifics of the course and the faculty offering it.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The screenshot shows the FLUP course page for 'Bachelor in Applied Languages'. The page is in Portuguese. It features a navigation menu on the left with options like 'Welcome', 'Organization', 'Courses', 'Academic Portal', etc. The main content area includes a header with the course name, a notice about accreditation, and several sections: 'General information' (with details like Official Code, Director, Acronym, Academic Degree, Type of course/cycle of studies, Start, and Duration), 'Study Plan' (with links to 'Study plan' and 'All Study Plans'), 'Certificates' (listing 'Bachelor of Arts in Applied Languages - Major in Translation (180 ECTS credits)' and 'Bachelor of Arts in Applied Languages - Major in Business Relations (180 ECTS credits)'), 'Main Scientific Areas' (listing 'Languages' and 'All classifications'), and 'Previous Courses/Cycles of Study' (listing 'ECCT - European Studies: Intercultural Communication and Translation'). A sidebar on the right contains 'Options', 'Documents', 'Academic calendar', 'Admissions Applications', 'Projects / Dissertations / Theses', 'Schedules', 'Teachers', 'Scientific Committee', and 'Monitoring Committee'.

Figure 45 . FLUP course page

Universidade de Coimbra – UC (University of Coimbra)

The University of Coimbra (UC) CC²² is directly provided as a result by Google search engine. Actually, this is a real CC with all the information recommended by the ECTS Users' Guide (Figure 13). Information about the institution and about the resources and services is included in the same website under the "ECTS Information Package" menu, available in Portuguese and English, which counts with info about:

- HOME
- INSTITUTIONAL INFORMATION
- COURSE CATALOGUE
- PRACTICAL INFORMATION
- ABOUT THE ECTS SYSTEM

²² UC CC website: <https://www.uc.pt/en/ects/catalogo/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

ECTS Information Package

HOME INSTITUTIONAL INFORMATION COURSE CATALOGUE PRACTICAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE ECTS SYSTEM

Course Catalogue

- [Undergraduate degrees](#) (1st cycle programmes)
- [Integrated master degrees](#) (integrated study cycles: 1st+2nd)
- [Master degrees](#) (2nd cycle programmes)
- [Doctorate/ PhD degrees](#) (3rd cycle programmes)

Course units taught in English by Faculty

If the Faculty you're looking for doesn't have a link, please contact the relevant [academic mobility coordinator](#).

- Faculty of Arts and Humanities
 - [Faculty of Economics](#)
 - Faculty of Law
 - Faculty of Medicine
 - Faculty of Pharmacy
 - Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences
 - [Faculty of Sciences and Technology](#)
 - Faculty of Sport Sciences and Physical Education
-
- [International study programmes](#) (programmes taught in English and other foreign languages and/or in partnership with foreign universities)

Figure 46. UC Course Catalogue

In the Course Catalogue, when selecting a cycle program, all courses from all faculties are displayed (Figure 14). This comprehensive approach enables users to explore the full range of courses available across different faculties within the university.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

COURSES / Pesquisa

Organisation Unit
- all -

Course type

- 1st Cycle Studies
- Integrated Study Cycle (1st and 2nd)
- 2nd Cycle Studies - Continuity Master Programme
- 2nd Cycle Studies - Advanced Specialisation Master Programme
- 2nd Cycle Studies - Lifelong Learning Master Programme
- 3rd Cycle Studies
- Non Degree Course

Courses (46)

<p>BG Bachelor's Degree in Geology 1st Cycle Studies</p>	<p>LA Bachelor's Degree in Anthropology 1st Cycle Studies</p>
<p>LBIOQ Bachelor's Degree in Biochemistry 1st Cycle Studies</p>	<p>LBIOL Bachelor's Degree in Biology 1st Cycle Studies</p>
<p>BCE Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering 1st Cycle Studies</p>	<p>BEE Bachelor's Degree in Environmental Engineering</p>

Figure 47 UC course by cycle of studies

Once students select a course, they can review several key characteristics of the bachelor's degree program, including its general objectives, admission requirements, career prospects, mode of delivery (full-time, part-time, or distance learning), language of instruction and evaluation, assessment methods, grading scale, exam regulations, course and departmental coordinators, as well as credit requirements and distribution across different subject areas (Figure 15).

COURSES / Department of Earth Sciences

← SEARCH OPEN WEBSITE

Bachelor's Degree in Geology

General Objectives of the Course

The bachelor in Geology is a professional who is able to work autonomously, to carry out geological mapping, to explore for natural resources, and to collaborate on studies in all areas of planning, land use, and natural hazards, and to collect, analyze, interpret and communicate geological information efficiently, not only for specialists but also for other audiences.

Admission Requirements

National Call for Access and Entry to Higher Education (DGES):

One of the following subjects:
02 Biology and Geology
09 Geography
16 Mathematics

Application score: 100 points (0-200 scale)
Entry exams: 95 points (0-200 scale)

Calculation Formula:
Secondary school average: 50%
Entry exams: 50%

Other forms of access (UC-applicants):
- Change of Institution / Course Pair Schemes;
- Special Access Call for over 23-years-olds;
- Special Access Call for Holders of Other Higher Education Courses;
- Special Call for International Students.

This information does not exempt the consultation of the webpage of the Directorate General of Higher Education (DGES) and/or of the Applicants website. Please, visit the [DGES](#) and the [Applicants websites](#)

Professional Goals

Companies and management consulting; municipalities, universities and national and international research centers, laboratories services, spatial planning, patrimony and teaching.

Study Programme

COMMON CORE

→ **Bachelor's Degree in Geology**

AREAS OF EXPERTISE

→ **Bachelor's Degree in Geology**

→ **Licenciatura em Geologia -
Percurso Ensino**

→ **Geology with Minor**

Academic year
2024-2025

Course Type
1st Cycle Studies

DGES Code: 9146

Qualification Awarded: *Bachelor's Degree*

Duration: 6 Semester(s)

ECTS Credits: 180.0

Applications

Call for Applications

[Holders of Other Higher Education Degrees
Over 23-year-olds](#)

Figure 48 . UC Course description

The UC course catalogue page boasts a user-friendly interface, facilitating effortless navigation and access to comprehensive course details, streamlining the exploration of academic options for students. Additionally, it ensures adherence to the ECTS Users' Guide, enhancing compatibility and standardisation across academic systems.

Universidade de Aveiro – UA (University of Aveiro)

The University of Aveiro (UA) presents a wealth of course information on its website²³, conveniently located under the "STUDYING" section of the menu (Figure 16). The website is provided in Portuguese and English, but some translations are missing as shown.

Visually, the website is well-organised, allowing students to easily select and view courses based on their degree preferences.

²³ UA website: <https://www.ua.pt/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The screenshot shows the University of Aveiro website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Prospective Students', 'UA Students', 'International Students', 'Alumni', 'UA People', and 'Society'. Below this is a dark header with the university logo and a main navigation menu including 'ABOUT UA', 'STUDYING', 'LIVING', 'RESEARCH', 'COOPERATION', and 'INTERNATIONAL'. A sidebar menu is open under 'STUDYING', listing options like 'courses', 'applications', 'teaching support', 'study support', 'internships and employment', and 'departments and schools'. The main content area is titled 'Courses' and is divided into two sections: 'Courses with degree conferencing' and 'Courses without degree conferencing'. The first section lists 'Licenciaturas', 'Master degrees', 'Doctoral programmes', and 'Integrated master courses in transition'. The second section lists 'Higher professional training courses', 'Graduate Specialisation Programmes', 'Advanced specialisation programmes', and 'Microcredentials'.

Figure 49 UA Courses

When selecting the desired study cycle, the University of Aveiro (UA) website provides a plethora of filtering options (Figure 17). These include the subsystem, city where the course is offered, scientific areas, and admission tests. This array of options offers more flexibility compared to previously observed websites, allowing for a tailored and refined exploration of available courses.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The screenshot shows the University of Aveiro website. The top navigation bar includes 'universidade de aveiro' and 'io' logos, and menu items: ABOUT UA, STUDYING (highlighted), LIVING, RESEARCH, COOPERATION, INTERNATIONAL. A search icon and 'PT' are also visible. A dropdown menu for 'studying' lists: courses, applications, teaching support, study support, internships and employment, and departments and schools. The main content area is titled 'Licenciaturas' and includes a descriptive paragraph: 'In Portugal, a "Licenciatura" degree corresponds to the first cycle of Higher Education, being a degree which can comprehend any area of studies. The cycle of studies leading to an undergraduate "Licenciatura" degree has a duration of six to eight semesters, which correspond to 180 and 240 ECTS units each.' Below this are four filter boxes: subsystem, city, scientific areas, and admission tests. A list of courses follows: Accounting, Accounting evening, Aerospace Engineering, Automation and Manufacturing Systems, Basic Education, Biochemistry, Biology, Biology and Geology, and Biomedical Engineering.

Figure 50. UA courses per cycle of studies

When selecting a specific course at the University of Aveiro (UA), we are directed to a detailed page containing a wealth of information. This includes an overview of the course, its objectives, and key features. It is possible to find:

- Contact information for the course director, facilitating communication for inquiries or assistance.
- Information about the department or school within the university that oversees the course is provided, along with details regarding the duration of the course, its mode of study, and any specific course offerings.
- Tuition fees for both national/EU students and international students, including any variations for different academic years, are outlined.
- Potential career paths and professional opportunities that graduates of the course may pursue. Statistics related to graduates' employment rates and career outcomes provide insight into the course's effectiveness in preparing students for the job market.
- Details about the course's accreditation status, including the accrediting body and accreditation date, are also available.

The UA course information is showcased through an interactive, visually captivating, and well-organised design, featuring various tables and colours (Figure 18).

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

universidade de aveiro

ABOUT UA
STUDYING
LIVING
RESEARCH
COOPERATION
INTERNATIONAL

 | [PT](#) |

studying

courses

applications

teaching support

study support

internships and employment

departments and schools

1st cycle degree in Accounting

Objectives

This Accounting degree aims to prepare graduates with solid knowledge in the area of accountancy and skills for working with Information and Communication Technologies. Its main objectives are:

- To provide the students with a solid grounding in accountancy, able to elaborate financial information systems and internal control systems, prepare and analyse financial, budgetary, analytical and fiscal information;
- To prepare qualified professionals able to work in organisational environments;
- To prepare professionals able to meet the demands and challenges of the new organisational and technological paradigms.

Curricular Plan

Director

[Sandra Maria Geraudes Alves](#)
sandra.alves@ua.pt

Departaments/Polytechnic Schools

[Institute of Higher Education for Accountancy and Administration](#)

Duration 3 years / 6 semesters	Mode Daytime	Course 1st cycle degree	National/EU student tuition fee 2023/2024 697,00€/year
Scientific area(s) Accounting	Subsystem	Teaching language(s) Portuguese	International tuition fees 2023/2024 4150€ /year

Admissions

Figure 51 . UA course description

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Slovenia

Slovenian universities have developed different practices in publishing the CC. Here is an example of two other public Slovenian universities.

Generic examples

University of Ljubljana

Information on the application and admission procedure and the CC is published in a document available in pdf. format at: <https://www.uni-lj.si/assets/Sluzba-za-mednarodno-sodelovanje/Dear-exchange-student-letter-2024-25.pdf>.

The document is unclear and very unfriendly to students, especially those with certain accessibility restrictions, due to the large number of links to CCs and contact persons.

The document contains a separate link for each member faculty to a web page with information on the CC. Each faculty has a completely different list of courses.

On some links the CC is not published at all or requires many additional clicks to access it. The following are examples of such bad practices:

The screenshot shows the website of the University of Ljubljana Academy of Music (UL AG). The navigation bar includes 'UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA Academy of Music', 'ACADEMY OF MUSIC UL', 'STUDY', 'ARTISTIC ACTIVITY', and 'INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION'. The main content area is titled 'EXCHANGE PROGRAMMES AND APPLICATION REQUIREMENTS'. It contains the following text:

Students who wish to apply to the UL AG as part of an international exchange programme, e. g. Erasmus+ must submit an application via the EASY platform of the AEC through the following link: <https://aec.dreamapply.com>. We will only be able to accept Erasmus applications sent to us digitally, through the EASY online tool. Students have to be nominated by their own institution. In case your home institution is not on the list of partner`s institutions, please contact the International officer from your institution or International Relations coordinator at UL AG, Nina Podlipnik nina.podlipnik@ag.uni-lj.si, +386 1 24 27 320. UL AG accepts all the applications, even the institutional agreement is not yet signed.

APPLICATION DEADLINE FOR WINTER SEMESTER (beginning of October until January) is MAY 15 and FOR SUMMER SEMESTER (middle February to June) is NOVEMBER 15.

UL AG also accepts students outside the Erasmus+ exchange programme, free movers and via bilateral agreements. Those students have to contact UL AG Internationa office: aginter@ag.uni-lj.si.

BROSHURE

Figure 52 Academy of Music, University of Ljubljana

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Nomination +

Course selection -

— Look through UL VF's course catalogue (curriculum) for the next academic year and assemble your proposed Learning Agreement for Studies.

Application +

Pre-arrival +

Figure 53 Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Ljubljana

Figure 54 Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Few faculties pay much attention to their CC and keep it well organised.
Here are some examples of a well-organised CC:

The screenshot shows the website of the Faculty of Arts at the University of Ljubljana. The page is titled "Academic year 2024/2025" and lists several courses in English. The courses are organized into a table with columns for Subject/Predmet, Department/Oddelek, Prerequisites, ECTS, Semester, and Prijava/Application. The courses listed are Modern Korean, Japanese Language in Practice, and Modern Chinese. The prerequisites for these courses are clearly stated, such as "required prior knowledge of Korean - *full year subject" for Modern Korean. The contact information for the courses is also provided, such as "jasna.bavec@ff.uni-lj.si".

Subject/Predmet	Department/Oddelek	Prerequisites	ECTS	Semester	Prijava/Application
Modern Korean 2*full year subject	Department of Asian Studies	required prior knowledge of Korean - *full year subject	9	Full year	jasna.bavec@ff.uni-lj.si
Japanese Language in Practice 1*full year subject	Department of Asian Studies	required prior knowledge of Japanese - *full year subject	6	Full year	jasna.bavec@ff.uni-lj.si
Modern Chinese - Language Tutorial 1*full	Department of Asian Studies	*full year subject	6	Full year	jasna.bavec@ff.uni-lj.si

Figure 55 Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana

No faculty of the University of Ljubljana includes any functionality in the CC that would allow filtering of courses and thus facilitate the search for relevant courses.
Some faculties publish the CC in a separate pdf. or Excel document.
Below are some examples of such a catalogue:

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Contacts | Library | Student-net | Intranet | EBookshop | Search...

RESEARCH & CONSULTING

Home > Incoming Exchange Students > Course catalogue

Study Programmes

- Doctoral students about courses
- Incoming Exchange Students
 - Course catalogue**
 - Practical Information
 - Application Process
- Academic Calendar
- International Projects and Events

Additional information:

Petra Burgar
Coordinator for Incoming Exchange Students
T: +386 1 5892 518
Office: D-222
incoming@ef.uni-lj.si

Additional links:

- ISEB LU Fact sheet - Contacts
- ISEB LU Fact sheet - Exchange students

1 od 157

COURSE CATALOGUE
Academic Year 2023/2024

University of Ljubljana SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS

Figure 56 Faculty of Economics, University of Ljubljana

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Home | Erasmus+ | Incoming Students | Erasmus Courses in English

course+catalogue+2023_2024.xlsx

ERASMUS+

Figure 57 Faculty of Maritime Studies and Transport, University of Ljubljana

Best CC example

University of Primorska

The University of Primorska has not yet developed an IT solution to support the electronic application of students for mobility.

The CC is published in a web application which allows a clear search of courses according to the following information (<https://www.upr.si/en/students-up/754-international-mobility/incoming-mobility/study-offer-for-mobile-students/list-of-courses-for-mobility-students/>):

- Faculty
- Level of study
- Area
- Language
- Semester

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

FACULTY	LEVEL	STUDY PROGRAM	AREA	SUBJECT	LANGUAGE	SEMESTER	CREDIT
Faculty of Humanities	Undergraduate (Bachelor degree) study programmes	Archaeology	022 Humanities	Archeology of the Early Stone Age	SI	W	6
Faculty of Humanities	Undergraduate (Bachelor degree) study programmes	Archaeology	022 Humanities	Culture of the East Mediterranean	SI	W	6
Faculty of Humanities	Undergraduate (Bachelor degree) study programmes	Archaeology	022 Humanities	Methodology of Archeological Research	SI	W	3
Faculty of Humanities	Undergraduate (Bachelor degree) study programmes	Archaeology	022 Humanities	Latin Language and basic Epigraphy 1	SI	W	3
Faculty of Humanities	Undergraduate (Bachelor degree) study programmes	Archaeology	022 Humanities	History and Teory of Archaeological Research	SI	W	3
Faculty of Humanities	Undergraduate (Bachelor degree) study programmes	Archaeology	022 Humanities	Foundations of ancient numismatics	SI	W	6

Figure 58 . Screen shot of the University of Primorska

The University of Primorska, like the University of Maribor, collects the CCs of all faculties and prepares one central CC.

The CC contains all the necessary information for the student, with the exception of course curriculum descriptions and learning outcomes.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Spain

Universities generally provide information about CCs to some degree, but VET centers do not include this information.

Table 1 includes a list of Spanish universities with information related to their CCs. This list is considered representative of the general situation in the country. Most universities have CC solutions similar to the 3 first universities (UVigo, UPM and UPN), while the last 3 last ones have the best CC found.

To be precise, just the UGR has a proper CC solution. The other universities have the CC information distributed on several locations of the institutional web site. In this way, in general all the information considered in the ECTS Users' Guide cannot be directly accessed. Another common trend is that individual educational components information is provided in the form of learning sheets. The preparation of learning sheets is included in the Spanish law of the University System²⁴ (article 6.2) and in the quality regulation for university studies²⁵ (article 9.3). Namely, it is a legal obligation for universities and the simplest way to provide course information.

Table 7 List of main representative CCs in Spain

Institution	CC Web address	Generic information	Resources and Services	Programmes	Individual Educational Components
Universidade de Vigo (UVigo)	Institutional web site https://www.uvigo.gal/	Fully available	Partially available	Partially available	Provided as Learning Sheets
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)	Institutional web site https://www.upm.es/	Fully available	Partially available	Partially available	Provided as Learning Sheets (PDF)
Universidad Pública de Navarra (UPNA)	Institutional web site https://www.unavarra.es/	Fully available	Partially available	Partially available	Provided as Learning Sheets
Universidad de Almería (UAL)	Institutional web site https://www.ual.es/	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available

²⁴ LOSU Organic Law, march 22, BOE-A-2023-7500. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/lo/2023/03/22/2>

²⁵ Royal Decree 822/2021, September 28, BOE-A-2021-15781 <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2021/09/28/822/con>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Universidad de Granada (UGR)	https://ugrcat.ugr.es/en/	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available	Fully available
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)	Institutional web site https://www.uoc.edu/es	Fully available	No available	Partially available	Provided as Learning Sheets

Generic examples

Universidade de Vigo (UVigo)

The Universidade de Vigo (UVigo) does not have a proper CC, but the information of the CC can be found in the institutional web site²⁶. The information is available at several places from the main menu: institutional information about the university, in the "UNIVERSITY" item; information about educational programmes, in the "STUDY" item; information about resources and services, in the "ON CAMPUS" item; specific information for international students and for exchange students, in the "COME TO VIGO" item. The information is included in Galician, Spanish and English languages.

Regarding the ECTS Users' Guide, the previous sections include much more information than the required one. The information is partially available but scattered on several web pages, and it is not easy to find some data. In addition, despite all the web pages follow the general style of the Uvigo Web site and some pictures are provided, they do not show an attractive style. The first pages include just links to other pages and very large pictures not clearly related to the topics addressed, see Figure 2.

²⁶ UVigo institutional web site: <https://www.uvigo.gal/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Study

Study at the Universidade de Vigo can be an unforgettable experience. We are a new but dynamic institution that scales nationally and internationally

Our University offers you a wide variety of official studies, both graduate and postgraduate programs. Other type of non-official studies -considered of the same importance- are also available, such as the Seniors university program, the Languages Centre or the complementary training of university extension.

What to study

- > Undergraduate programs
- > Master programs
- > PhD programs
- > Lifelong Learning
- > Seniors university program
- > Online learning
- > Expired degrees
- > Implementation and modification of degrees

Access

- > Access to Undergraduates
- > Access to Masters

Study

What to study

Access

Academic organization

We advise you

Students management

Employability

ÚLTIMAS NOVAS

O II Torneo de Debate Retórica UVigo reunirá a vindeira semana en Vigo 90 estudantes de 12 universidades

Figure 59 . Screen shot of programmes page in the UVigo web site

Programmes information is provided in an organized and simplified way, a kind of programme profile as it is shown in Figure 3, including data about: key features, such as credits, modality and number of courses, knowledge area, coordinator, a short summary, the teaching plan with the list of courses and teachers, admission process, professional opportunities, information regarding mobility and applicable regulations. Most of the information are links to other pages: the faculty or school where the programme is provided, the teacher profiles in the institutional web site, the subject information available in another web site, links to the international relationships offices, etc. Therefore, key information is missed and not provided directly. In addition, notice some of the information is not properly translated into English. The information about programme structure and credits is not presented. In addition, no visuals are provided, and the view is not attractive.

As it has been indicated, the information on courses is provided in a different website, containing learning sheets. All the information is provided as text in formatted tables. For each academic year it is provided a different learning sheet. The information included in the learning sheets is: year of the course, quadmester in which it is provided, mandatory or optional character, number of credits, teaching language, prerequisites, department, coordinator with contact, lecturers, web site for

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

teaching, general description, training and learning results, expected results, contents, planning, methodologies, personalized assistance (tutoring), assessment, sources of information and recommendations. This is the information provided for general students.

Another important thing is this information is provided by faculty and school. Therefore, all the programmes provided by the same faculty or school are provided together. Nevertheless, a broader view of the whole university programmes is not offered at this level.

TELECOMUNICACION

Características

Campus: Vigo
 Tipo: Undergraduate program
 Créditos ECTS totais: 240
 Modalidade: Presencial
 Prazas: 130
 Número de cursos: 4
 Código: V05G301V01

Área de coñecemento

Área de Enxeñaría e Arquitectura

Faculties

> [Escola de Enxeñaría de Telecomunicación](#)

Contacto

✉ mcurty@com.uvigo.es
 > [Ir á web da titulación](#)

Coordination of the degree

> [Marcos Curty Alonso](#)

Undergraduate programs

Master programs

PhD programs

Lifelong Learning

Seniors university program

Online learning

Expired degrees

Implementation and modification of degrees

MÁS INFO	PLAN. DOCENTE	ACCESO ADMISIÓN
v Descripción		
v Saídas profesionais		
^ Mobilidade		
> More information in International		

Figure 60 . Screen shot of a programme page in the UVigo CC

The UVigo CC contains more of the information required by the ECTS Users' Guide, but the information is dispersed in several different sections and it is not provided in an attractive and homogeneous way. The information on programmes is rather scarce and most of the sections

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

contain links to other sites not directly related or well-integrated with the CC. The information on courses is provided in a different site as learning sheets with a completely different style. There are many inconsistencies in the information provided and some of the translations are not available. Users may get lost easily and the general learning experience could be improved in many ways.

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)

Similar to the previous case, The Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) does not have a proper CC provided as a result by the Google search engine, but the CC information can be found at the institutional web site²⁷ and at several faculties and schools websites. Indeed, the Google search engine provides as result a link to the CC of Telecommunication Engineering School of this university. The information is available at several places of the institutional web site: institutional information about the university, in the "UPM" item; information about educational programmes in the "STUDENTS" item, "Students and Degrees" subsection, see Figure 4; information about resources and services is dispersed in the previous sections. The previous information is included in Spanish and English languages.

The information provided in the previous sections is rather scarce, in textual form and usually it requires to click in many links to arrive to it. For example, the information about programmes just includes the number of credits, the objectives, the general objectives, the school in which it is provided and a link to the web page of the programme. All this information is shown in a single page. There is no information about the programme structure, subjects, etc. In addition, all the information is provided in a textual form and some of the information is not translated.

In the web sites of the engineering schools of the UPM there are more information about the programmes and courses offered, for example in the Telecommunication Engineering School web site²⁸, see Figure 5. This page includes some pictures and more information that is provided in a more attractive way. Data as number of credits, duration, language and academic coordinator and contact are included. Other data is provided in specific sections: career opportunities, program educational objectives, students data from recent courses (incoming students and enrolled student) and access to higher students. It is also provided the syllabus of the program, with the distribution of credits in subjects, the list of subjects per semester and their credits and links to the course information.

The course information is provided as a learning sheet in a PDF document. No website is provided for this information.

²⁷ UPM institutional web site: <https://www.upm.es/>

²⁸ UPM Telecommunication Engineering School CC at its web site:
<https://www.etsist.upm.es/internacional/incoming-students/course-catalogue>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

UPM Channel | Español | Studies and Degrees

UPM | Students | Researchers

UPM Channel | Español | Studies and Degrees

Universidades Españolas.com UCRANIA European University

UPM / Studies and Degrees

01. Academic life

02. Grants and Aid

03. Studies and Degrees

- ▶ Official Undergraduate Degrees
- ▶ UPM Undergraduate Degrees
- ▶ Double Degrees
- ▶ Official Master Degrees
- ▶ PhD
- ▶ Own postgraduate courses

04. Incoming Students

05. Exchange Mobility Programs

06. Student Attention

07. Special Insurance Scheme for Students

08. Cultural Activities

09. Employment and Practicing

10. University Library

11. Course Catalog in English

Studies and Degrees

- ▶ Official Undergraduate Degrees
- ▶ UPM Undergraduate Degrees
- ▶ Double Degrees
- ▶ Official Master Degrees
 - ▶ Admission
 - ▶ Enrollment
 - ▶ Calendar
 - ▶ Master programs
 - ▶ Frequently asked questions
- ▶ PhD
 - ▶ Admission
 - ▶ Enrollment
 - ▶ Calendar
 - ▶ PhD programs
 - ▶ Thesis
 - ▶ Forms
- ▶ Own postgraduate courses

f | |

Figure 61 . Screen shot of programmes page in the UPM web site

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

ESCUOLA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE
INGENIERÍA Y SISTEMAS DE TELECOMUNICACIÓN
UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

Intranet | News | Contact | Spanish

Telemática
Campus Sur

POLITÉCNICA

The School | Programs | Students | Research | International | Internships and employment

Programs / B.Eng. in Data Engineering and Systems

01. Student Outcomes
02. Syllabus
03. Horarios, calendarios y exámenes
04. Profesorado
05. Acreditación y verificación
06. Recursos y servicios
07. Gestión de calidad
08. Evaluación Curricular
09. Actividades Acreditables
10. Preguntas frecuentes (FAQ)

B.Eng. in Data Engineering and Systems

From the academic year 2024/25, the Degree in Data Engineering and Systems is only offered for new students within the **Double B.Eng. Diploma in Data Engineering and Systems and Telematics Engineering**.

GRADO EN INGENIERÍA Y SISTEMAS DE DATOS

More information about B.Eng. in Data Engineering and Systems
[Promotional WEBSITE](#)

Basic characteristics

- Credits: 240 ECTS
- Duration: 4 years (8 semesters)
- On-campus: Yes

Figure 62 . Screen shot of programmes page in the Telecommunication Engineering and Systems of UPM

The general impression from the UPM is that the information about CC has not been planned at an institutional level. The information is scarce, dispersed, available at different levels according to the language and provided in not a very attractive way. Inside the university, at least some school has made an effort to provide CC information in a more attractive way, at least at the programme level. Nevertheless, the information on courses is very scarce just available as PDF documents containing learning sheets.

Universidad Pública de Navarra

Similar to most of the previous cases, the Universidad Pública de Navarra (UPN) also has its CC information scattered on several pages of the institutional web site²⁹. Nevertheless, searching in Google for this university CC provides as first result a link to the CC page as part of the international relations and cooperation section, international relations and mobility>international students

²⁹ UPNA institutional web site <https://www.unavarra.es/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

subsection, see Figure 12. This page contains a list of programmes arranged by faculties and schools. Information about the institution can be found under the item "THE UNIVERSITY" and sub-item "Governing structure"; information about resources and services under the item "SERVICES". There is also a specific section for foreign students under the "PROFILE" item. The different pages follow a variety of styles regarding to the presentation of the information. The information is available in Basque, Spanish and English languages.

International Relations and Cooperation

Figure 63 Screen shot of the main web page of the Universidad Pública de Navarra CC

Regarding to the programmes section, this information is provided in a very clear way in a single web page, with a single picture at the top but with structured text, see Figure 12. Text is provided in an enriched form: plain, bold and with links. The list of subjects per year of the programme is provided indicating the semester in which the subject is provided, code, name, ECTS and the language in which the subject is provided. Core and optative courses are clearly identified. Some information is missed. A menu on the left side of the programme page includes a menu with access to the full list of faculties/schools and programmes of the university.

The course information can be accessed from the list of courses in the programme. It is provided as a learning sheet in a different web site. The information provided is the following one:

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

competences, learning results, methodology, activities, languages, assessment, contents, topics, experimental practices, bibliography, place of teaching.

Modules and professors

More information about the degree

- Presentation
- Modules and professors**
- Assessment
- Final-year undergraduate Project
- Academic information
- Study programmes
- Timetables and classrooms
- Internships
- Diploma quality and indicators

Curriculum code: 505 - List of Core and Compulsory subjects - (2023/2024)

Personalised information on your tutor.

Click ✓ to get detailed information on each subject

On each row of the following table you will find information on the first year subjects, organised by terms. You will get to know about which subjects may be taught in Spanish, Basque or English, and access the subject information by clicking on each language

FIRST YEAR						
Periodo	Code	Subject	ECTS	SPA	BAS	ENG
1º S	505101	LINEAR ALGEBRA	6	✓		
1º S	505102	CALCULUS I	6	✓		
1º S	505103	BIOLOGY	6	✓	✓	

Figure 64 . Screen shot of the main web page of the Universidad Pública de Navarra CC

The UPNA has many of the information required by the ECTS Users' Guide for the CC. Nevertheless, it cannot be considered as one of the Best CC examples because all the information is scattered around many places and the information is not complete. In any case, the information on programmes is provided in a clear way and the user navigation is simple.

Best CC examples

Universidad de Almeria (UAL)

Similarly to the previous three examples, the University of Almeria (UAL) also has the CC information scattered on several locations of the institutional website³⁰. As it can be observed in the menu of the main page, see Figure 6, it is offered information on programs, in the "Academics and

³⁰ UAL institutional web site: <https://www.ual.es/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Admission” item; information on resources and services, in the “Life at UAL” item; and information about the institution, in the “About” item. All the information is available in Spanish and English. The programmes web page contains all the bachelor’s and master’s degrees of the university arranged by knowledge area. Double university and International double degrees are included in specific sections. When a specific degree is clicked, a new page is opened with information about such programme.

Figure 65 . Screen shot of the main web page of the UAL CC

The information about a specific program is provided in a very well-structured and attractive way, see Figure 7. A main menu includes items for: Presentation, Curriculum, Guidance, Mobility and Quality Assurance. Direct access is provided to information about the academic calendar, timetables and exams of the programme. The pages include enriched formatted text (plain, bold and links) with images, links to documents and in many cases tables and structured information. Next it is described the content of each section in a more detailed way:

- The presentation section is a kind of profile of the degree, including information about the accreditation of the degree; the suggested profile for newly enrolled students; general data such as branch of knowledge, duration in credits and years, type of education, language(s) used, level of study (ISCED), coordinator and contact, objectives and competencies and mentions included in the degree; professional and academic opportunities; professional qualification; and reports about the degree and links to official documents and regulations. All these information is provided in a very attractive way with different text styles, columns

and table arrangements. The information is neither scarce nor overwhelming. Links to reference documents and more detailed information are provided where appropriate.

- The curriculum section includes a submenu with the following options:
 - Subjects. This provides a list of courses arranged by year. For each course it is provided the code, name, number of ECTS and character (core, compulsory, optional).
 - Structure and distribution of credits. A table is included at the top of this page with the number of ECTS per year and character. Next, a textual description of the programme structure is described with references to modules, mentions, etc.
 - Prerequisites and Corequisites. This page contains information about requirements for courses, particularly for the dissertation. Courses that need to be enrolled previously or simultaneously are indicated. Corequisites regarding subject to be enrolled simultaneously and exclusive corequisites for which simultaneous enrolment is prohibited are also provided. This information is in some cases just in Spanish..
 - Accreditation of Language Competence (B1). Language requirements to get the degree and information on how to obtain it.
 - Coordination. Identification of the degree's coordinators, including telephone number and e-mail address. Link to the general regulations of the degree.
 - Degree Tutorings. Information about the tutors available and their functions. Link to the regulations and application forms.
 - Curricular internships. Information on internships, including internships coordinator(s) and regulations. Information is provided regarding curricular internship management, resolutions, calendar, tutors, etc.
 - Bachelor's Dissertation. Description of this project, regulations, calendar, documents of interest, application forms, dissertation submission, assessment and defense panels, etc.
 - Recognition and Credit Transfer. General information and links to regulations. A functionality to check recognitions on several universities is provided.
 - Adaptation of the Curriculum. Information related to the adaptation of the previous to the new bachelor programme.
- Information about guidance provided in the degree. Some of the information is not available in English. It is arranged as follows:
 - Guidance. It provides text about guidance available for new students and for already enrolled students and links to some other web pages.
 - Access and admission. A general page of the UAL about access and admission to any programme.
 - Enrollment. A general page of the UAL about enrollment in any programme.
 - Grants and Aids. A general page of the UAL about grants and aids.
- Mobility. Provides information about the student mobility opportunities in the programme and a link to the open calls from the UAL. It is also provided a search functionality to find available student exchange programmes available for the degree. For each exchange

programme is provided: destination university, coordinator, comments, vacancies, duration, language and country. Exchange programmes available include: Erasmus+ Movilidades Internacionales: Erasmus+ KA131: Student Mobility for Studies (SMS); Erasmus+ Estudios UAL KA171 (antes KA107); UALMUNDO-Programa Propio de Movilidad Internacional; ANUIES-CRUE-Programa de movilidad Académica con Universidades Mexicanas; SICUE-Sistema de Intercambio entre Centros Universitarios Españoles.

- Quality Assurance. Provides information about the Quality Assurance System (QAS) available and links to regulations and reports.

Regarding courses the CC includes the following information:

- General data: code, character, year, period, ECTS, implementation year.
- Data of the academic year: module, matter, department, area, coordinator.
- Teaching guides of all the years. Just in Spanish. It is provided a link to a PDF.
- Exams: date, hour, classroom and comments.
- Teaching groups. For each group schedule and classroom.
- Working groups. For each group schedule and classroom.

A breadcrumb is included to facilitate the navigation through the CC.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Presentation

Important:

- [Document to help you register.](#)

EURO-INF.

This bachelor's degree is accredited by the European Quality Assurance Network for Informatics Education (EQUANIE) through the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA) with the international quality label

The bachelor's degree in Computer Engineering comprises studies that have a notably multidisciplinary content, giving graduates the appropriate training to cover computer issues from various fields of knowledge.

Figure 66 . Screen shot of a programme web page of the UAL CC

The UAL includes much more information about programmes and courses than the required by the ECTS Users' Guide. Double university and International double degrees are highlighted in the web site. Many of the information provided is not just for prospective or visiting students, but also for students already enrolled. All the information is provided in a very structured and attractive way, according to the same style. Enriched format text (plain, bold and links), with images and tables are included to facilitate users' reading and make the pages more attractive. The navigation among the different sections is clear and users can move around the different programmes and courses without getting lost.

Universidad de Granada (UGR)

The Universidad de Granada (UGR) CC is directly provided as a result by Google search engine. Actually, this is a real CC with all the information recommended by the ECTS Users' Guide. Information about the institution and about the resources and services is included in the same web

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

site under the “ABOUT the UGR” menu. Another menu item available as “COMMENTS AND SUGGESTIONS” provides a form to submit comments and recommendations. A third menu item named as “ABOUT UGRCAT” provides general information about the catalogue itself.

The information provided in the CC main web page³¹, see Figure 8, includes a search functionality and a list of programmes arranged by branch of education (Arts and Humanities, Sciences, Health Sciences, Social and Legal Sciences, Engineering and Architecture), in the bottom part of the page. It is possible to search programmes or courses. Information on courses and programmes can be directly accessed from this main page. When the user searches for some word, a results page is provided with the programme/course name, code, program type and branch of education. It is also available a functionality to browse and filter the results. The information is available in Spanish and English languages.

PROGRAMME CATALOGUE (2023/2024)

Figure 67. Screen shot of the main web page of the UGR CC

³¹ Web site of the UGR CC <https://ugrcat.ugr.es/en/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

The programme information is provided in a very clear and organized, see Figure 9. All the information is provided in a single page with a menu in the left to go directly to specific part of the page.

The menu contains the following sections:

- General information. This is provided in a formatted table with information about:
 - Academic year, ECTS credits, level of qualification (EQF), level (e.g. bachelor), length of the programme in years, model of study, type, mode of delivery, mobility window. A link to academic information for mobility students is included. It is also included information about the work-based learning (practicum) availability.
 - More info. A link to other web page is provided where all the subjects of the programme are listed with a link to the learning sheet. This new page is just in Spanish.
 - Programme coordinator. Identification of the person and e-mail address.
- Field(s) of education and training. According to ISCED-F.
- Main focus. A short paragraph.
- Competences. A list of competences.
- Qualification. Name of the title awarded in original language. Qualification requirements and access to further studies.
- Programme Courses. A list of all the courses of the programme, with indication of the year and period. It is possible to filter the courses by year and period.
- Admission information. A list of degrees/diplomas or studies, or any equivalent to a provided list.
- General regulations. About the grading and examination, with links to relevant documents.
- The programme page also includes a comments and suggestion form.

MASTER'S DEGREE IN TEACHER TRAINING FOR COMPULSORY AND UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION, VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING (VET) AND LANGUAGE TEACHING

Programme code: SG1561 Creation date: 21/11/2023 / Last update: 21/11/2023

ABOUT THIS PROGRAMME

General information

ISCED-F Fields

Main focus

Competences

Qualification

Courses

Specialisations

Admission information

Regulations

COMMENTS AND SUGGESTIONS

General information

Academic year: 2023/2024	Level: Master	Type: Official Master's Degree
ECTS Credits: 60	Programme orientation: Professional	Length of programme (full time): 1 YEAR
Mode of delivery: Face-to-face	Level of qualification: Máster (MECES level 3 - EQF level 7)	Model of study: Full-time (42-60 ECTS per school year)
Mobility windows: Optional Academic Information for mobility students	Work-based learning (Practicum): Yes	Language(s) of instruction: Spanish
PROGRAMME COORDINATOR		
Name: JUAN MANUEL, MARTÍN GARCÍA / jmarting@ugr.es		
Faculty of Arts / Granada campus		

FIELD(S) OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING (ISCED-F)

- Teacher training with subject specialization (0114)

Figure 68 Screen shot of a programme page of the UGR CC

For each course it is provided a similar web page following the style of the programme one. It is included information on:

- Programme: course code, reference to the programme.
- General information: name, teaching period, mode of delivery, academic year, course type, ECTS, year of study, language(s) of instruction.
- School/faculty and campus in which the subject is provided. A link is included.
- Course guide. A link to the learning sheet that opens in a new page. The learning sheet is just in Spanish.
- Course content (descriptor). A list of course contents.
- The course page also includes a comments and suggestion form.

The UGR CC follows the ECTS Users' Guide recommendations. It does not include enriched textual information with many links to other documents and images. In any case, the clean style is very appropriate to get the key information. In every page is included information on the creation date, last update and a comments and suggestion functionality.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)

The Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC) renewed its CC in 2023³². As in previous cases, a proper CC is not found, but in the institutional web site³³ there are plenty information about programmes and courses under the “Course Offering” menu item. The previous page indicates that the university offers 323 programmes, see Figure 9: bachelor’s degrees, master’s degrees, lifelong learning master’s degrees and postgraduate courses, specialization diplomas and expert diplomas, and doctoral programmes. Nevertheless, just 6 doctoral programmes and several master’s degrees, postgraduate and specialist courses are fully included in the website with all their data. The information is available in Catalanian, Spanish and English.

Figure 69 Screen shot of the main web page of the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya CC

The renewal of the CC in the UOC was part of the transformation of the university’s digital ecosystem with a focus on external users and an attempt to respond to the needs of its primary audiences. The new CC is intended to attract future students based on an excellent user experience, SEO and mobile-first design which encourages the discovery both on and beyond the portal of their courses. In any case, this renewal seems part of an ongoing process that is not still finished. The CC does not include information about all the programmes provided by the UOC, particularly no bachelors’ degree programme is included. Similarly, the information provided on courses is offered in a

³² “UOC course catalogue site updated and ready for users” <https://www.uoc.edu/en/news/2023/093-course-catalogue-site-uoc>

³³ UOC institutional web site: <https://www.uoc.edu/>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

completely different style. Some announced functionalities such as a browsing engine and a comparison between programs was not found.

Some of the new functionalities and features included in the new CC are:

- All the programme information is provided in a single page, that can be browsed using available main menu options available on top and submenu options available at each subsection.
- The content is provided according to a flexible information architecture. Information is arranged in sections and subsections, but not all of them are included for all the programmes.
- Many visual contents are provided, with pictures of the programme structure, courses arranged by type, pictures of the programme's deans and a clear and attractive organization.
- A browsing functionality is available for master's programmes with options to filter by: knowledge area, knowledge sub-area, type of programme and registration options.
- SEO and SEM strategies have been implemented to enhance overall visibility.

Regarding to the ECTS Users' Guide contents, this CC includes:

- In the main page information about the university:
 - Specific information of the institution as "a pionerring online university". History, accreditations, position in the rankings, alliances, etc.
 - The educational model of the university based on an e-learning approach.
 - Information for students about how to enrol.
- The institutional information about the rector and governing bodies is available from the top menu, item "About us: a pioneering online university", sub-item "Organization and governing bodies".
- Information on Resources and Services was not found. Nevertheless, this makes sense as it is a distance university and students are not going to live in a campus or university location.
- Information on programmes is organized mainly around the following programmes and options:
 - Postgraduate programmes, specializations and expert diplomas.
 - Doctoral programmes and research.
 - Language courses.

All the information for a programme can be downloaded as a single PDF or browsed online based on the following menu options:

- Presentation. Provides a brief summary of the program, start date, next enrollment date, number of credits and languages in which the programme is provided. It is also included a link to the enrollment place and information on the official qualification awarded.
- Academic programme. The information in this section is different depending on the programme. In some cases, it includes the list of courses but without access to further information about the individual courses, duration of the whole programme and academic pathway in a very visual way with a diagram showing specializations and

possible routes to follow along the programme. In other cases, see Figure 10, it is included a list of the courses organized by type (basic, compulsory, optional and final project) and providing access to detailed information about each course (shown in a separate web page), and information about workload, practices and final degree project.

- Credit recognition. This section is not included in every programme.
- Academic team. Including the name and pictures of the dean management. For the other related personal (direction of the programme, staff and collaborators) in some cases it is provided a short CV, a link to an online profile page or anything at all in most cases.
- Career opportunities. It is provided information about objectives and employability, profiles, competencies, who is addressed to? And professional outing.
- Access requirements. It includes information about the requirements to be admitted to the programme, prior knowledge and degree.
- Enrollment and fees. Provides information about the enrolment process and price, payment options, discounts and free enrollment insurance.
- From some of the programmes it is possible to get access to the course (individual study components) information. Nevertheless, this information is provided in a separated web page with a different appearance that the one provided in the CC site. Actually, the course information is provided as learning sheets. The learning sheet contents can be accessed from some menu options available on top: view general information, description, the subject within the syllabus as a whole, professional fields to which it applies, prior knowledge, information prior to enrolment, learning objectives and results, content, view the UOC learning resources used in the subject, additional information on support tools and learning resources, guidelines on assessment at the UOC and view the assessment model.

The screenshot shows the 'Programme of Study' page for UOC. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the UOC logo and various links: 'About us: a pioneering online university', 'Research and innovation', 'Open knowledge', 'Global impact #2030Agenda', 'Course offering', 'EN', a search icon, 'Request information', and 'Campus'. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with tabs: 'Presentation', 'Study plan' (selected), 'Credit Recognition', 'Academic team', 'Career opportunities', 'Access requirements', and 'Enrolment and fees'. The main heading is 'Programme of Study'. A large box displays the ECTS breakdown: 60 ECTS total, consisting of 24 ECTS Optional, 30 ECTS Mandatory, and 6 ECTS Final work. Below this are sub-menus for 'Subjects', 'Workload', 'Practices', and 'Final degree project'. The 'Courses' section is partially visible, showing a table with 'Types of courses' and 'Credits'. The table has one row: 'Basic courses' with a credit value of 60.

Figure 70 . Screenshot of the UOC CC with the nemus on the top for the main sections and the sub-menus in the Programme of Study section.

In summary, this example shows the efforts and interest of an online university to enhance the information provided on the university and academic offer for prospective students. In this particular case, as a distance e-learning university, the UOC does not seem interested on attracting visiting (e.g. Erasmus) students, but students that can be in the university for the whole programmes. Nevertheless, this example also demonstrates the great challenges and difficulties regarding this goal. The provided system was launched in 2023, but it is far from being complete neither in contents nor functionalities. Some of the general aspects found in the proposal are: an structured information model with optional sections and subsections, large amount of visual contents to provide and attractive interface, and a simplified navigation through a single page.

Other examples

The Government of Spain launched an initiative in 2008 to provide a resiter of universities, centers and programmes (RUCT³⁴: *Registro de Universidades, Centros y Títulos*). This register was created to provide the most relevant information about universities, centers and programmes in the Spanish University system. Regarding to programmes, "Sección títulos", it is provided a search functionality that offers information about programmes at all the levels. For each programme it is provided the

³⁴ RUCT web site: <https://www.educacion.gob.es/ruct/home>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

academic level, level of study (Spanish MECES), knowledge area, professional qualification, ECTS credits, and references to legal documents and states. As it can be observed, the amount of information is very reduced considering the ECTS Users' Guide.

Use cases

These use cases/functionalities have been identified in the reviewed CCs:

To search the CC for programmes or courses including filtering options for the results.

To browse the CC for programmes or courses including filtering options.

To include forms to enable users(students) to do some tasks:

- Check internships.
- Check final studies dissertation.
- Check recognitions and credit transfer from other universities.
- Mobility opportunities. The user can select the desired country where to go and the system provide a list of available options.

To include a functionality for comments and suggestions for the whole CC and for individual sections.

In addition, the following features has been observed and could be taken into account:

All the information provided in a single web page with a menu to go directly to some sections.

To include enriched text with links, images, tables, etc.

Requirements

In the UAL we checked that not all the programmes provide the same information. Depending on the programmes some fields were not shown because they had no information.

Last update date should be included for the information.

Estonia

Tallinn University's (TLU) ÕIS2 CC (link in Table 1) and user guides for Students and Lecturers are publicly available on TLU home page³⁵. Incoming Exchange Courses are brought out and listed separately on the Incoming Exchanges page (link in Table 1), making it easy for exchange students to find and select courses before arrival, compared to searching from the ÕIS2 CC. After arrival to TLU Exchange Students can create a user account and access ÕIS2 for course registration.

The list of Incoming Exchange Courses on TLU web page is updated twice a year. The Incoming Mobility Senior Specialist centrally collects the course information via an Excel file in Google Drive from all Departmental Erasmus Coordinators and uploads the received course information to the home page. The courses can be searched by academic unit (Figure 1). On each units page the course information - level, code, title, ECTS, assessment form and comments - is displayed and links to course descriptions are available (Figure 2).

The academic units of Tallinn University offer the following courses for exchange students:

[Baltic Film, Media and Arts School](#)

[School of Digital Technologies](#)

[School of Educational Sciences](#)

[School of Governance, Law and Society](#)

[School of Humanities](#)

[School of Natural Sciences and Health](#)

In addition, students can join some courses offered by [Academy+](#)

Figure 71 . Screenshot of the TLU Exchange Courses page - the part with links to each academic units courses page

³⁵ ÕIS2 user guides for Students and Lecturers: <https://www.tlu.ee/en/ois>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

https://www.tlu.ee/en/school-digital-technologies

TALLINN UNIVERSITY

ABOUT US / ADMISSIONS / **STUDIES** / RESEARCH / COOPERATION / MEDIA / TRAINING / TRAINING AND CONFERENCE CENTRE

Incoming Exchange Studies

Applying for Exchange Studies

Exchange Courses

Baltic Film, Media and Arts School

School of Digital Technologies

School of Educational Sciences

School of Governance, Law and Society

School of Humanities

Please contact the Departmental Erasmus Coordinator for further information about the offered courses: Ms. Maria Saar | maria.saar@tlu.ee | +372 6 409 354 | Room: A-431 (Astra).

By clicking on the title of the course you will be taken to the course outline, which provides basic information about the course. Assessment form "Exam", means the course is graded (A-F); "Assessment" means the result is marked P (pass) or MA (fail).

Autumn Semester 2023/2024

Level	Code	Title	ECTS	Assessment Form	Comments
BA	IFI6099.DT	Computer Games	4	Exam	
BA	IFI6023.DT	Computer Graphics	4	Exam	
MA	IFI7180.DT	Prototyping	4	Assessment	
MA	IFI7219.DT	Software Engineering and Design	4	Exam	

Figure 72 . Screenshot of the Exchange Courses page of the School of Digital Technologies

University of Tartu does not have Incoming Exchange courses separately brought out on the home page. Instead the courses with English as the language of instruction are easily searchable in the public CC in ŌIS2 (link in Table 1). Figure 3 shows the search engine, where it's possible to look for courses by language of instruction as well as a number of other parameters. On Figure 4 a search result example is shown, with unit and language of instruction used as parameters. From the search result page course description pages with thorough information about each course can be opened easily by clicking on the course tabs.

UNIVERSITY OF TARTU

Dashboard
Timetables
Courses
Curricula
Continuing education
Academic calendar

Detailed search

Part of title

Course code

Faculty/institution

Lecturers

Language of instruction: English

Language training

Year: Year Semester: Semester

Form of teaching

Levels of study

Form of study

State

In-depth Estonian language learning Can be taken by continuing education learners?

Figure 73 Screenshot of the CC search engine of the University of Tartu.

UNIVERSITY OF TARTU

Dashboard / Courses

Courses

Search by course title, code, etc.

Course versions

Detailed search

Unit: Institute of Computer Science Language of instruction: English

Showing 48 results. Scroll down to load more results

Cryptography II MTAT.07.003 6 ECTS	Bioinformatics Seminar MTAT.03.242 12 ECTS
Design and Analysis of Algorithms MTAT.03.286 6 ECTS	Didactic Practice MTAT.00.023 6 ECTS
Didactic Practice MTAT.00.042 3 ECTS	Intelligent Transportation Systems MTAT.08.040 6 ECTS

Figure 74 CC search results view, University of Tartu.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

TalTech's ÖIS2 system allows search by language of instruction, which is useful for prospective Exchange Students and quite easy to use (see Figure 5). Of course other search parameters are also available. The search results come with links to course descriptions.

The screenshot shows the TalTech ÖIS2 system search results page. The search parameters are set to 'English' and 'Lecturer's language of instruction'. The results table is as follows:

no.	Course code	Course	Lecturer	Study semester	E-support level
1.	ITX0025	Introduction to Information Technology	Endre Domiczi (English)	autumn	
2.	MES0080	Hydraulics and Pneumatics	Vladimir Kuts (English, Estonian)	autumn	2
3.	YFX9030	Individual Studies Centered on Research Topic	Jaan Kalda (English)	autumn - spring	

Figure 75 CC search results view, TalTech.

Table 8 List of main CCs in Estonia

Institution	CC Web address	Course descriptions	Language of instruction	Incoming exchange CC Web address
Tallinn University	https://ois2.tlu.ee/tluois/uus_ois2.tud_leht	linked	no information	https://www.tlu.ee/en/courses
University of Tartu	https://ois2.ut.ee/#/courses	linked	yes	n/a
TalTech	https://ois2.taltech.ee	linked	yes	https://taltech.ee/en/courses-english

Tallinn University and TalTech have made it very easy for prospective Exchange Students to find information about Incoming Exchange Studies on their home pages (Figures 6 and 7). Along with relevant practical information and guidelines also Exchange Courses can be easily found. Tallinn

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

University lists the Exchange Courses directly on the homepage with links that lead directly to the course descriptions as we've seen on Figure 2. TalTech, however, lists Exchange courses along with links in an Excel file as shown on Figure 8.

The screenshot shows the TLU home page with the following navigation menu items: CONTACTS, ESTONIAN, RUSSIAN, TALLINN UNIVERSITY, ABOUT US, ADMISSIONS, STUDIES (highlighted), RESEARCH, COOPERATION, MEDIA, TRAINING, TRAINING AND CONFERENCE CENTRE. The main content area features several categories:

- Study Allowances and Scholarships:** Study Allowances, Ministry of Foreign Affairs Scholarships
- Academic calendar**
- Incoming Exchange Studies:** Applying for Exchange Studies, Exchange Courses, Once you Have Arrived, During Your Studies, Before Leaving, Departmental Erasmus Coordinators, Traineeship at Tallinn University, Contacts
- Counselling**
- Outgoing Exchange Studies:** Erasmus+ Exchange Studies in Europe and outside of the European Union, Bilateral agreements, Erasmus+ Traineeship, International Summer and Winter schools, Scholarships for exchange studies, Going on studies abroad on your own initiative, Internationalisation at home
- External studies**
- Recommendations for the Use of Artificial Intelligence**
- Practical Matters:** Accommodation
- Feedback system:** OIS feedback system

Figure 76 . Incoming Exchange Studies menu on TLU home page.

The screenshot shows the TalTech home page with the following navigation menu items: Admissions, Student (highlighted), Research, Cooperation, About the University. The main content area features a 'STUDENT' menu with the following items:

- Freshmen
- Academic information >
- Counselling >
- Tuition & Financial Aid >
- Exchange Studies >**
- Student Life >
- Seminars
- Outgoing >**
- Incoming >**
- Visiting Students >
- Erasmus Charter
- Contacts
- Before Mobility >**
- Academic Information >**
- Citizenship and residence issues >
- Practical Information >
- Scholarships
- Welcome Week
- FAQ
- Academic Calendar for Exchange Students
- Courses in English
- Grading System
- Academic Policies at TalTech
- Changing Learning Agreement
- Registration to Exams

Figure 77 . Incoming Exchange Studies menu on TalTech home page.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Course code	Title of the Course	EC	Assessment form	Lowest study level	Number of accepted student	Prerequisite
VAY0900	Management Psychology and Theory	3	Pass/fail assessment	Bachelor's studies		
VAY0910	Organizational Behavior and Public Relations	6	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VLL0540	Maritime English L IV	3	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VLL1170	Maritime English L I	6	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VLL1180	Seamanship and Ship Maintenance	3	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VLL1190	Maritime Conventions	3	Pass/fail assessment	Bachelor's studies		
VLL1250	Maritime English STCW	3	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VLL1300	Cargo handling	6	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VLL1480	Introduction to Cyber Security	6	Pass/fail assessment	Bachelor's studies		
VLM0500	Marine Steam and Gas Powerplants	3	Examination	Bachelor's studies		
VME0400	Environmentally sustainable shipping	6	Examination	Master's studies		
VME0500	Concepts of Economics	6	Examination	Master's studies		2 Basic math

Figure 78 TalTech Incoming Exchange CC.

University of Tartu does not have Incoming Exchange Studies information separately brought out on their website. Instead one can find information for international students interested in applying to do a full programme in UT, as can be seen on Figure 9. Prospective Exchange Students can find course information through the ÕIS2 public CC search, as was shown on Figure 4.

UNIVERSITY OF TARTU

Quick links ▾ All UT contacts Accessibility 🔍 Search

Admissions **Studies** Research Business International About us News and media Alumni

- Studies
 - Academic calendar
 - Getting started
 - Study info >
 - Cost of tuition
 - Stipends and allowances
 - Student support >
- Student support
 - Especially for international students >
 - Psychological counselling
 - Career counselling
 - Counselling students with special needs and making adaptations in...
- Especially for international students
 - ABC for arrivals
 - Visa and residence
 - Contacts
 - Tartu Welcome Centre

Figure 79 . UT information for international students.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

One additional CC example is an information system developed in and specifically for Tallinn University's School of Digital Technologies to enable alternative ways of sharing, displaying and searching of information compared to ÖIS2. This system is named DigiÖIS³⁶ and in addition to other information it also lists all the courses provided by the school and displays the language of instruction in case it's English.

Compulsory courses 16 ECTS						
	ECTS	Autumn 2023	Spring 2024	Autumn 2024	Spring 2025	Responsible lecturer
DTI7002.DT	Research Methods	6	6			Pirgit Sillaots
IFI7065.DT	Master's Thesis Seminar I	3	3			Linda Helene Sillat
IFI7066.DT	Master's Thesis Seminar II	3			3	Kairit Tammets
IFI7229.DT	Data Analysis: Descriptive and Inferential Statistics	4		4		Paula Joanna Sillat
Elective module: Development Processes and Supporting Learning at Organisations and Networks						
Compulsory courses 24 ECTS						
	ECTS	Autumn 2023	Spring 2024	Autumn 2024	Spring 2025	Responsible lecturer
IFI7074.DT	Technology-enhanced Learning in Organization	4	4			Kai Pata
IFI7226.DT	Digital Transformation Project in Organizations and Networks	6		6		James Sunney Quaicoe
IFI7352.DT	Cooperation and Co-Creation in Digital Environments	4	4			James Sunney Quaicoe
KAN7056.HR	Adult Training and Development Process Management. Management of Private Adult Training Company.	6	6			
KAN7067.HR	Leadership in Development Processes	4	4			
Elective module: Design of Learning Games						
Compulsory courses 24 ECTS						
	ECTS	Autumn 2023	Spring 2024	Autumn 2024	Spring 2025	Responsible lecturer
IFI7302.DT	Basics of Game Development	4		4		Ahmed Mohamed Said Anwar Elshenawy

Figure 80 . Example of DigiÖIS - courses in English marked with Union Jack.

Generic examples

Tallinn University brings Exchange Courses out separately in an easily accessible form, but the information needs to be uploaded and updated manually. Searching courses directly from a CC that's at the same time used by the HEI as an everyday tool for official study information, would make a lot more sense, but TLU public ÖIS2 page does not enable course search by language of instruction.

TalTech offers both options - courses with English as the language of instruction can easily be found in the public CC, as was shown on Figure 5, and on the homepage Exchange Courses are brought out separately. TalTech uses an Excel table for listing Exchange Courses with links to course descriptions in ÖIS2.

Best CC examples

The best public ÖIS2 course catalogue from the three HEI-s seems to be the one used and developed by the University of Tartu. Nevertheless, as UT does not separately bring out courses

³⁶ DigiÖIS: <https://dti.tlu.ee/digiois/index.php?lang=en>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

suitable for Exchange Students, it may be somewhat unclear as to which courses accept Exchange Students and which do not (of any).

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Czechia

Here is a table of the Czech universities taken into account in this report.

Table 9 List of main CCs in Czechia

Institution	CC Web address	Generic information	Resources and Services	Programmes	Individual Educational Components
Charles University	https://is.cuni.cz/studium/eng/peredmety/index.php	Fully available	Average availability	Fully available	Fully available
Masaryk University	https://czs.muni.cz/en/student-from-abroad/international-student-guide/course-catalogue	Fully available	Average availability	Fully available	Average availability
West Bohemian University	https://portal.zcu.cz/ects/?lang=en	Fully available	Average availability	Fully available	Average availability

Here are screenshots of the webpages of these universities hosting their course catalogs, illustrating their commitment to providing accessible and comprehensive academic information:

Best CC examples

Charles University and Masaryk University are continually working to enhance their Course Catalogues (CCs) to provide students with increasingly comprehensive and valuable information. Both universities are committed to ensuring that their CCs serve as useful tools for students seeking information about available courses, study programs, and academic opportunities. Through ongoing efforts, they aim to enrich the content of their CCs with detailed descriptions of courses, program requirements, learning outcomes, and additional resources to support students in making informed decisions about their academic pathways. By prioritizing the continuous improvement of

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

their CCs, Charles University and Masaryk University demonstrate their dedication to enhancing the academic experience and facilitating the success of their students.

Charles University, Masaryk University, and West Bohemian University are all committed to enriching their Course Catalogues (CCs) to offer students comprehensive insights into their academic offerings. While Charles University and Masaryk University are prominent institutions in the Czech Republic, West Bohemian University plays a vital role in higher education as well. Notably, West Bohemian University contributes not only to the development of its own CC as part of their study information system but also collaborates with numerous other Czech universities to enhance their study systems. This collaborative effort ensures that the CCs of all three institutions are continually improved with detailed course descriptions, program requirements, and other essential information. By actively developing its system not only for its own benefit but also for a wide range of other universities, West Bohemian University underscores its commitment to providing students across the Czech Republic with valuable resources to support their academic endeavors.

Charles University

The screenshot shows the 'Subjects' interface with search filters and a table of results. The filters include Title, Annotation, Syllabus, Faculty (Faculty of Humanities), Department, School, Class, Classification, 4EU+, Virtual mobility, Key competences, Language (English), Semester, Display (20 results per page), and Teacher(s). The table below lists the search results.

Code	Title	Semester	Language of instruction	Form of teaching	Hours per week, examination	E-Credits	Department	Enabled for web enrollment	Virtual mobility	Capacity	4EU+
YBAC16	A Social and Cultural History of Communist Europe Told Through Communist Humor	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 0/4, MC [HT]	6	24-AJ EXT	no	no	no	no
YBEC119	Academic Reading and Writing	both	English	full-time	0/2, MC [HS]	3	24-KO	yes	no	no	no
YMG5537	Academic Reading and Writing	both	English	full-time	0/2, Ex [HT]	3	24-KOS	no	no	no	no
YD009	Academic Writing	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 0/0, Ex [HT]	0	24-OSD	yes	no	no	no
YMPD001	Academic writing and presentation skills	winter	English	full-time	winter s. 1/1, MC [HT]	3	24-TVP	no	no	no	no
YBEC008	AJ - Intermediate	both	English	full-time	0/2, MC [HT]	3	24-KO	yes	no	no	no
YBEC012	AJ - Listening Skills (Intermediate)	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 0/2, MC [HT]	3	24-KO	yes	no	no	no
YBEC153	AJ - Upper-Intermediate II.	both	English	full-time	0/2, MC [HT]	3	24-KO	yes	no	no	no
YBAJ083	Animation Design with Moviestorm	winter	English	full-time	winter s. 0/18, MC [HS]	3	24-SHVAJ	yes	no	no	no
YBAJ235	Anthropological Methods: Fieldwork and Ethnography (Lecture)	winter	English	full-time	winter s. 2/0, MC [HT]	4	24-SHVAJ	yes	no	no	no
YBAJ234	Anthropological Methods: Fieldwork and Ethnography (Seminar)	winter	English	full-time	winter s. 0/2, MC [HT]	2	24-SHVAJ	yes	no	no	no
YBAJ245	Anthropological Perspectives on Kinship	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 2/0, MC [HT]	4	24-SHVAJ	yes	no	no	no
YDEA001	Anthropology and Ethics	both	English	full-time	0/12, Ex [HS]	0	24-DAE	no	no	no	no
YMSKA41	Anthropology of Tourism and Mobility	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 2/0, MC [HT]	5	24-KOA	yes	no	no	no
YBAJ175	Anthropology of Tourism and Mobility	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 0/2, MC [HT]	4	24-SHVAJ	yes	no	no	no
YMG5505	Argumentation and Academic Discourse	winter	English	full-time	winter s. 0/2, C [HT]	4	24-KOS	no	no	no	no
YBAU051	Art History and Spiritual Values in Central Europe	summer	English	full-time	summer s. 0/4, MC [HT]	6	24-AJ EXT	yes	no	no	no
YBAJS201	Bachelor Thesis Defense	both	English	full-time	0/0, thesis [HT]	0	24-SHVAJ	no	no	no	no
YBE014	Bachelor's Thesis Preparation	both	English	full-time	0/0, C [HT]	20	24-SHVAJ	no	no	no	no
YBAU049	Behavioral Economics	winter	English	full-time	winter s. 0/4, MC [HT]	6	24-AJ EXT	no	no	no	no

Figure 81 Charles University's CC

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Masaryk University

The screenshot displays the 'Subjects' portal interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Subjects (version: 945)' and 'Course, academic year 2023/2024'. Below this, a search bar and navigation links for 'Search', 'Teachers', 'Departments', 'Classes', 'Classification', and 'View by plans' are visible. The main content area is titled 'Details' and shows information for the course 'Anthropology and Ethics - YDEA001'. Key details include: Title: Anthropology and Ethics; Guaranteed by: PhD Applied Ethics (24-DAE); Faculty: Faculty of Humanities; Actual: from 2020; Semester: both; E-Credits: 0; Examination process: written; Hours per week, examination: 0/12; Capacity: winter/unknown / unknown (unknown) (3); summer/unknown / unknown (unknown) (2); Min. number of students: unlimited; 4EU: no; Virtual mobility / capacity: no; Key competences: State of the course: taught; Language: English; Teaching methods: full-time; Level: Note: you can enroll for the course repeatedly; course is intended for doctoral students only; can be fulfilled in the future; you can enroll for the course in winter and in summer semester. At the bottom, there are sections for 'Annotation - English' and 'Syllabus - Czech', both with their respective last update dates. A footer at the very bottom contains 'contacts' and 'Charles University | Information system of Charles University | http://www.cuni.cz/UKEN-329.html'.

Figure 82 . Masaryk University's CC

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Course Catalogue

Courses taught in English can be found on the websites of Masaryk University's faculties. See the links below and choose courses you would like to attend during your mobility. Find out more about the grading system and the exam organization at Masaryk University [here](#).

The course catalogues also provide further details on each course (open course syllabus after clicking on the course code). There are details about the course teachers, objectives, learning outcomes and number of ECTS. Moreover, it also lists course extent and intensity (You can see three numbers for course intensity. The first is the number of hours for lectures, the second is for class exercises/seminars and the last stands for other teaching methods such as labs, etc.).

ERASMUS STUDENTS, PLEASE NOTE: If you choose courses from a different department than you were nominated to, your LA may or may not be approved by your departmental coordinator, but they cannot guarantee that those courses will be taught.

- **Faculty of Law:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Medicine:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Science:** [Autumn semester](#) and [Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Arts:** [Autumn semester](#) and [Spring semester](#)
 - (see also special link to courses for students accepted by the [Department of English and American Studies](#); [Studies](#) > [Info for foreign students](#))
- **Faculty of Education:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Pharmacy:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Economics and Administration:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Informatics:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Social Studies:** [Autumn semester](#) and [Spring semester](#)
- **Faculty of Sports Studies:** [Autumn and Spring semester](#)
- **Central European Studies Programme (CESP):** [Autumn semester](#) and [Spring semester](#)

Please note that **there might be further changes** due to teachers' availability, numbers of students registered for the courses, etc. **You can make changes to your Learning Agreement after your arrival – change your IS enrolment within 2 weeks from the beginning of the semester and your Learning Agreement in the following week.**

Academic calendar

EXPLORE IT

International student guide

GUIDE ME

Get Android or iOS app: Navigation through MU

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

FF:AJ29850 Master's Thesis - Course Information

AJ29850 Master's Thesis

Faculty of Arts
Autumn 2024

▣ **Extent and Intensity**

0/0/0. 0 credit(s). Type of Completion: z (credit).
Taught in person.

▣ **Guaranteed by**

prof. Mgr. Jan Chovanec, Ph.D.
Department of English and American Studies – Faculty of Arts
Contact Person: Tomáš Hanzálek
Supplier department: Department of English and American Studies – Faculty of Arts

▣ **Course Enrolment Limitations**

The course is only offered to the students of the study fields the course is directly associated with.

▣ **fields of study / plans the course is directly associated with**

there are 14 fields of study the course is directly associated with, display

▣ **Course objectives**

Submission of master's thesis

▣ **Syllabus**

- Submission of master's thesis

▣ **Literature**

- GIBALDI, Joseph. *MLA handbook for writers of research papers*. 6th ed. New York: Modern Language Association of America, 2003, xviii, 361. ISBN 0873529863. info

▣ **Teaching methods**

Consultations arranged on an as-needed basis; standard is three 30 minute sessions.

▣ **Assessment methods**

Submission of master's thesis according to the Study Regulations and the Department requirements. Upon submission, the supervisor gives the credit; by doing so, the thesis is proclaimed ready for the defence.

▣ **Language of instruction**

English

▣ **Further Comments**

The course is taught each semester.

The course is also listed under the following terms Autumn 2005, Spring 2006, Autumn 2006, Spring 2007, Autumn 2007, Spring 2008, Autumn 2008, Spring 2009, Autumn 2009, Spring 2010, Autumn 2010, Spring 2011, Autumn 2011, Spring 2012, Autumn 2012, Spring 2013, Autumn 2013, Spring 2014, Autumn 2014, Spring 2015, Autumn 2015, Spring 2016, Autumn 2016, Spring 2017, Autumn 2017, Spring 2018, Autumn 2018, Spring 2019, Autumn 2019, Spring 2020, Autumn 2020, Spring 2021, Spring 2022, Autumn 2022, Spring 2023, Autumn 2023.

- Enrolment Statistics (Autumn 2024, recent)
- Permalink: <https://is.muni.cz/course/phil/autumn2024/AJ29850>

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

West Bohemian University

University of West Bohemia

These websites are part of the ECTS information catalogue. They contain a basic description of study programmes and study branches offered at university including standard study plans. Descriptions of particular courses are also included.

For better user orientation and convenience we have provided a variety of ways to choose from while searching for information about study programmes and branches or when selecting courses. It is possible to search for information about programmes and courses either by using the given paths (see below) or it is possible to search by selecting attributes (see right).

Tools of the tables may be sorted by columns by clicking icons in the header. In case the icon of a bubble is shown, hovering the mouse over it will show details.

Plans search

Faculty - full name: %

Study programme name: [input]

Branch of study name / specialization: [input]

Form of study: %

Level of acquired qualification: %

Qualification awarded: %

Language of instruction: %

[Search]

Course search

Course code: [input]

Course title: [input]

Semester: %

Course content: [input]

Language of instruction: %

[Search]

Browse:

- Faculties
- Study programmes
- Study fields
- Courses

Faculty - full name

- Faculty of Applied Sciences
- Ladislav Sutnar Faculty of Design and Art
- Faculty of Economics
- Faculty of Electrical Engineering
- Faculty of Arts
- Faculty of Education
- Faculty of Law
- Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
- Faculty of Health Care Studies

Browse:

- Education fields names
- Study plans
- Courses

Education branch name

- Law, legal and public administration proceeding
- Physics courses
- Informatics courses
- Philological sciences
- Mathematics courses
- Electrical engineering, telecommunication and IT
- Art and applied art
- Special and interdisciplinary fields
- Business in areas and branches
- Philosophy, theology
- Physical education and sport

Browse:

- Education fields names
- Courses

Education branch name

- Law, legal and public administration proceeding
- Physics courses
- General professional training
- Mining and mining, geology, metallurgy and foundry industry
- Informatics courses
- Philological sciences
- Mathematics courses
- Electrical engineering, telecommunication and IT
- Psychology courses
- Architecture
- Art and applied art

Browse:

- Faculties
- Departments
- Courses

Faculty - full name

- Faculty of Applied Sciences
- Ladislav Sutnar Faculty of Design and Art
- Faculty of Economics
- Faculty of Electrical Engineering
- Faculty of Arts
- Faculty of Education
- Faculty of Law
- Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
- Faculty of Health Care Studies
- Institute of Applied Language Studies

University of West Bohemia

COURSE: FUNDAMENTALS OF MATHEMATICS 1

» [LIST OF FACULTIES](#) » [FAV](#) » [KMA](#)

Course title	Fundamentals of Mathematics 1
Course code	KMA/9ZM1
Organizational form of instruction	Lecture + Tutorial
Level of course	unspecified
Year of study	not specified
Semester	Winter and summer
Number of ECTS credits	4
Language of instruction	Czech
Status of course	unspecified
Form of instruction	Face-to-face
Work placements	This is not an internship
Recommended optional programme components	None

Lecturer(s)

- Šedivá Blanka, RNDr. Ph.D.

Course content

Mathematical reasoning - open statements and quantifiers; sets and elementary operations; subsets of real numbers. Vectors and its interpretation and using. Matrix calculus polynomial and exponential functions. Local and global behaviour of a function. Limits of functions; one-sided limits; algebra of limits. Continuity of a function at a point; product rule and chain rule. Applications of differential calculus in solving optimization problems. Indefinite integral; fundamental theorem of calculus; integration by parts and domain, graph. Applications of calculus of more variables in economy.

Learning activities and teaching methods

Interactive lecture, Task-based study method, Students' self-study, Practicum

- Contact hours - 52 hours per semester
- Preparation for formative assessments (2-20) - 20 hours per semester
- Preparation for comprehensive test (10-40) - 32 hours per semester

prerequisite

Knowledge

Figure 83 West Bohemian University's CC

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Summary

Generic examples in every country

France:

In France, many Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) either develop custom-made IT solutions for their course catalogs (CCs) or utilize the AMETYS Campus software. AMETYS Campus is an open-source platform that facilitates data management for education and local authorities. Several universities, such as Université Savoie Mont-Blanc, Université de Toulouse, and Université Paris Cité, have adopted this platform.

A generic example is the University of Reims Champagne Ardennes (URCA), which strives to meet European standards and provides a satisfactory level of information in its CC. The English version of their website allows users to search for courses by degree level, although detailed information often reverts to the French language version.

Greece:

Greek universities generally present information about their CCs with varying degrees of completeness. The University of Thessaly (UTH) offers a streamlined and user-friendly CC for courses offered in English, consolidating essential information on a single web page. Each department provides direct links to detailed course descriptions, semester schedules, and ECTS points.

Portugal:

In Portugal, the Instituto Politécnico de Porto (IPP) provides a comprehensive and accessible CC. The IPP's website features a detailed course catalog organized by departments, making it easy for students to navigate and find relevant information. The Polytechnic Institute of Porto's CC is a good example of how Portuguese institutions present their academic offerings in an organized and user-friendly manner.

The Course Catalogue about to be introduced belongs to the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (referred to as BME from here on), an internationally acclaimed HEI of considerable size, hosting many students on mobility. This type of CC is the most common nationwide. It is a collection of formatted PDF files, grouped by faculty (or other unit type) containing the list of courses available to incoming students.

To find the Course Catalogues, a Google search for the term "BME course catalogue erasmus" is effective. The course catalogue page contains links to general information, application information, application procedures, and links to course catalogues by organizational units. Navigating the course catalogue involves opening PDF files per faculty, which contain the available courses for the next academic year. Course information includes subject code, subject name, requirements, ECTS credits, course type, course code, course language, and timetable information.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Slovenia:

Slovenian universities have developed different practices in publishing the CC. Here is an example from the University of Ljubljana:

The information on the application and admission procedure and the CC is published in a document available in PDF format. However, this document is unclear and user-unfriendly, especially for students with certain accessibility restrictions, due to the large number of links to CCs and contact persons. Each faculty has a different list of courses, and in some cases, the CC is not published at all or requires many additional clicks to access it.

Examples of such practices include:

- Academy of Music, University of Ljubljana
- Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Ljubljana
- Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana

Few faculties pay much attention to their CC and keep it well organized. Examples of a well-organized CC include:

- Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana

No faculty of the University of Ljubljana includes any functionality in the CC that would allow filtering of courses, making it difficult to search for relevant courses. Some faculties publish the CC in a separate PDF or Excel document.

Examples of such catalogues include:

- Faculty of Economics, University of Ljubljana
- Faculty of Maritime Studies and Transport, University of Ljubljana

Spain:

Many universities in Spain follow a common approach where the Course Catalogs (CCs) are available on their official websites. These catalogs typically provide basic information about the courses offered, such as course titles, descriptions, credit hours, and sometimes prerequisites. However, they may lack advanced search features or comprehensive details, making it challenging for students to navigate and find specific information efficiently.

Estonia

In Estonia, many universities, like Tallinn University and University of Tartu, use their internal information systems (such as ÕIS2) to host their Course Catalogs (CCs). These catalogs typically provide basic information about courses, including titles, descriptions, credit hours, and sometimes prerequisites. However, the accessibility and organization of this information may vary between institutions, and some may lack features specifically tailored for exchange students.

Best CC examples in every country

France

One of the best examples of a CC in France is provided by the Université de Montpellier. Their CC is fully available online, including detailed information specifically tailored for international students. The site is well-organized, with sections dedicated to resources, services, and individual educational components.

Greece

The University of Crete (UoC) has one of the best CC solutions in Greece. Their online catalog is fully available and includes comprehensive information about all programs and individual courses, meeting most of the ECTS Users' Guide standards.

Portugal

The Directorate-General for Higher Education (DGES) in Portugal offers an excellent CC through their course assistant tool. This platform allows users to search for courses across various universities and provides detailed information on programs and individual courses, including ECTS points and prerequisites. Additionally, the University of Porto (U.Porto) provides a highly detailed and accessible CC that is well-regarded for its completeness and user-friendliness.

Hungary

Eötvös Loránd University (referred to as ELTE from here on) provides an exemplary CC, which is interactive, filterable, and searchable. It contains course and program information in a navigable web page format. To find the course catalogue, a Google search for "ELTE course catalogue" is effective. The ELTE International Course Catalogue page allows filtering by faculty, program, semester, and active semesters. The course catalogue provides various views, including a list view, an overview, and a details view, each offering specific information about courses and programs.

Slovenia

The University of Primorska has developed an efficient and user-friendly CC. The CC is published in a web application, which allows a clear search of courses according to faculty, level of study, area, language, and semester. The University of Primorska, like the University of Maribor, collects the CCs of all faculties and prepares one central CC. This CC contains all the necessary information for the student, with the exception of course curriculum descriptions and learning outcomes.

Spain

The University of Granada (UGR) in Spain provides a good example of a comprehensive and well-structured CC. Their online catalog is easily accessible through a dedicated website and offers detailed information about each course, including course objectives, content, assessment methods,

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

and recommended literature. The catalog is user-friendly, allowing students to search for courses by department, academic year, or keyword. Additionally, it provides links to related resources and support services, enhancing the overall student experience.

Estonia

Tallinn University (TLU) stands out as a good example of accommodating exchange students through its ÖIS2 CC and dedicated web pages. TLU's ÖIS2 CC includes course information and is complemented by a separate page listing Incoming Exchange Courses. This makes it easy for exchange students to find and select courses before their arrival. Additionally, the system allows exchange students to create user accounts for course registration upon arrival, enhancing the overall experience.

Czechia

The universities, including Charles University, Masaryk University, and West Bohemian University, are dedicated to continuously improving their Course Catalogues (CCs) to provide students with comprehensive and valuable information. They aim to enrich the content of their CCs with detailed descriptions of courses, program requirements, learning outcomes, and additional resources to support students in making informed decisions about their academic pathways. The collaborative effort among these universities ensures that the CCs are continually improved with essential information, demonstrating their commitment to enhancing the academic experience and facilitating the success of their students.

Other examples

France

An example of a less comprehensive CC is provided by Campus France. Despite its goal to present study programs from French HEIs, the catalog has been plagued with technical errors and inconsistencies, making it difficult for users to access complete and up-to-date information.

Greece

The National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (UOA) offers a CC that, while comprehensive in some areas, has information scattered across various sections of their website. This fragmentation makes it challenging for users to access all necessary information in a cohesive manner.

Portugal

The University of Minho (UMinho) provides a CC that, although detailed, often lacks the user-friendly organization seen in other institutions like the University of Porto. This can make navigation and information retrieval more difficult for users.

Hungary

Although the BME CC is common and provides necessary information, its PDF format limits interactivity and ease of navigation. Searching for specific courses can be cumbersome, requiring users to either read through documents or use a browser's search function, which is not as efficient as integrated search features in more advanced systems.

Slovenia

The University of Ljubljana's CC often lacks organization and user-friendliness. The document is unclear and difficult to navigate, with many links to separate CCs and contact persons, making it especially challenging for students with accessibility restrictions. Some faculties do not publish their CC at all, or require multiple additional clicks to access the information. Examples of less user-friendly practices include the Academy of Music, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, and Faculty of Electrical Engineering at the University of Ljubljana.

Spain

Some universities in Spain, such as the Universidad de Vigo (UVigo), may offer a less-than-optimal CC experience. Their CC information may be scattered across multiple web pages or documents, making it difficult for students to locate relevant information. Additionally, the presentation of course details may be inconsistent or incomplete, leading to confusion among students. Without a clear and organized CC structure, students may struggle to plan their academic paths effectively and access necessary course information.

Estonia

The University of Tartu, while having a comprehensive public ÖIS2 CC, lacks a separate section for Incoming Exchange Courses on its homepage. This can potentially make it unclear for exchange students to identify courses suitable for their exchange programs. Without a clear indication of which courses accept exchange students, navigating through the catalog may be challenging and could lead to confusion.

Conclusion

The report on Course Catalogue (CC) mapping across European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) reveals a diverse landscape with both challenges and opportunities. Analyzing CCs from France, Greece, Spain, Portugal, Slovenia, Hungary, Czechia, and Estonia has uncovered key findings that have implications for academic mobility and institutional collaboration within the European Higher Education Area (EHEA).

Each country has its own unique CC structures and policies, reflecting their distinct educational frameworks and regulatory environments. This diversity emphasizes the need for tailored approaches when harmonizing CCs across Europe to support mobility programs like Erasmus+. Despite the differences, common challenges were identified, including the need for timely updates, ensuring accuracy and completeness of information, and addressing inconsistencies in data presentation. These challenges can hinder students' ability to make informed decisions and navigate their academic pathways effectively.

Furthermore, there are huge differences between universities within the same country, which complicates the harmonization process even further. Additionally, it has been observed that within many universities, specific departments hold significant power and are often resistant to change, complicating efforts to implement unified platforms. This means that theoretically, all departments should be on board with migrating to a new platform, highlighting the necessity of a unified approach to ensure effective CC management.

The use of robust online platforms for CC management is crucial. These platforms must be user-friendly, accessible, and integrated with other institutional systems to facilitate seamless information dissemination. However, there is significant variation in the technological capabilities and user experience provided by different HEIs. Ensuring quality and regulatory compliance remains a priority across all HEIs. National quality assurance agencies play a pivotal role in overseeing the standards of CCs, thereby impacting their content and structure. However, achieving a balance between institutional autonomy and regulatory requirements is a recurring theme.

The study identified several exemplary models of CCs that stand out due to their comprehensive content, user-friendly design, and effective integration with institutional processes. These best practices can serve as benchmarks for other institutions aiming to enhance their CCs.

Developing standardized guidelines for CCs that can be adapted to the unique contexts of different countries would help in harmonizing practices across Europe. This includes standardizing the format, structure, and essential content elements of CCs. Investing in advanced technological solutions to create dynamic and interactive CC platforms can greatly improve user experience. Features such as integrated search functions, multilingual support, and mobile accessibility should be prioritized. Establishing protocols for regular updates and quality checks of CC information is essential. Institutions should implement mechanisms for continuous monitoring and improvement of their CCs to ensure accuracy and relevance. Promoting collaboration among HEIs to share best

practices, technological innovations, and strategies for effective CC management can foster a more cohesive approach. Collaborative efforts can also support capacity building in institutions with limited resources. Designing CCs with a student-centric approach ensures that they meet the needs of all stakeholders, particularly students. This involves incorporating feedback from end-users and continuously adapting to their evolving requirements.

In conclusion, the effective management and dissemination of CCs are critical to enhancing academic mobility and collaboration within the EHEA. By addressing the identified challenges and leveraging the outlined recommendations, HEIs can improve the accessibility, quality, and user experience of their CCs, ultimately contributing to the broader goals of educational equity and internationalization. Moreover, establishing a unified platform that includes all course catalogs from every university would be highly beneficial. Such a platform would streamline information access, facilitate smoother academic mobility, and ensure that students and educators alike can easily navigate the diverse educational opportunities across Europe.

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Bibliography

Agência de Avaliação e Acreditação do Ensino Superior. (2024). A3ES - Agência de Avaliação e Acreditação do Ensino Superior. Retrieved from: <https://www.a3es.pt/>

Cedefop (2023). Vocational education and training in Spain: short description. Luxembourg: Publications Office. Retrieved from: <http://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/221364>

Direção-Geral do Ensino Superior. (2024). DGES - Direção-Geral do Ensino Superior. Retrieved from: <https://www.dges.gov.pt/pt>

Faculdade de Letras da Universidade do Porto. (2024). FLUP - Faculdade de Letras da Universidade do Porto. Retrieved from: https://sigarra.up.pt/flup/pt/web_page.inicial

Education and Youth Board. (2024, May). International cooperation and education in Estonia. The Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Estonia. Retrieved from: <https://harno.ee/en/about-news-contacts/about/international-cooperation-and-education-estonia>

Haridussilm.ee. (2024, May). The Estonian Education Information System (Eesti Hariduse Infosüsteem, EHIS). Retrieved from: <https://www.haridussilm.ee/ee/tasemeharidus/oppetasemed/korgharidus/ylevaade>

Instituto Politécnico do Porto. (2024). IPP - Instituto Politécnico do Porto. Retrieved from: <https://www.ipp.pt/>

Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto. (2024). ISEP - Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto. Retrieved from: <https://www.isep.ipp.pt/>

McGrath, W. E., & Durand, N. (1969). Classifying courses in the university catalog. *College & Research Libraries*, 30(6), 533-539.

Ministère de l'Éducation nationale, de l'Enseignement supérieure et de la Recherche (2015). Référentiels de compétences des mentions de licence. Retrieved from: https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/content_migration/document/Referentiels_de_compétences_licence_formatMESR_2014_12_29_ssblancs_380001.pdf

Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Estonia. (2024, May). ESTONIAN SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION. Retrieved from: https://www.hm.ee/sites/default/files/documents/2022-10/higher_education_system_2010.pdf

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Estonia. (2024, May). Higher education). Retrieved from: <https://www.hm.ee/en/education-research-and-youth-affairs/general-education/higher-education>; in Estonian: <https://www.hm.ee/korgharidus-ja-teadus/korgharidus>

République française (2014). Arrêté du 22 janvier 2014 fixant le cadre national des formations conduisant à la délivrance des diplômes nationaux de licence, de licence professionnelle et de master. Retrieved from: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000028543525>

Selvaraj, A., Radhin, V., Nithin, K. A., Benson, N., & Mathew, A. J. (2021). Effect of pandemic based online education on teaching and learning system. International Journal of Educational Development, 85, 102444.

Study in Estonia. (2024, May). Education and Youth Board, the Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Estonia. Retrieved from: <https://www.studyinestonia.ee/>

Tallinn University. (2024, May). The University in Numbers - Studies (Ülikool arvudes - Õppetegevus). Retrieved from: <https://www.tlu.ee/en/studies>; in Estonian <https://www.tlu.ee/oppetegevus>

TalTech. (2024, May). Figures and reports. Retrieved from: <https://taltech.ee/en/figures-and-reports>

Tümen Akyildiz, S. (2020). College Students' Views on the Pandemic Distance Education: A Focus Group Discussion. International Journal of Technology in Education and Science, 4(4), 322-334.

Universidade de Aveiro. (2024). UA - Universidade de Aveiro. Retrieved from <https://www.ua.pt/>

Universidade de Coimbra. (2024). UC - Universidade de Coimbra. Retrieved from <https://www.uc.pt/>

Universidade de Lisboa. (2024). ULisboa - Universidade de Lisboa. Retrieved from <https://www.ulisboa.pt/>

Universidade do Minho. (2024). UMinho - Universidade do Minho. Retrieved from <https://www.uminho.pt/>

Universidade do Porto. (2024). U.Porto - Universidade do Porto. Retrieved from <https://up.pt/>

University of Tartu. (2024, May). University of Tartu Statistics. Retrieved from: https://statistika.ut.ee/ut/?inputs_&keel=%22en%22&uhis_check=false&voorkeelne_check=false

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**